

AKSUM UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE
Department of Agricultural Economics

**Value Chain Analysis of Beef Cattle: The Case of Tahtay Koraro Woreda
District, Tigray, Ethiopia**

By
Tesfay Abraha

**A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillments of the Requirements for the
Masters of Science Degree in Agribusiness and Value Chain Management**

Major advisor: Yassin Ibrahim (PhD)

Co-advisor: Girma Gezimu (Msc)

Shire, Ethiopia

June, 2015

DECLARATION

This is to certify that this thesis entitled “Value Chain Analysis of Beef Cattle: The Case of Tahtay Koraro North-Western Zone Tigray, Ethiopia.” submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of MSc., in Agribusiness and Value Chain Management to the College of Agriculture, Aksum University, through the Department of Agricultural Economics, done by Mr. Tesfay Abraha Hailemariam. A/CU/SE/PG/10/13 is an authentic work carried out by him under my guidance. The matter embodied in this project work has not been submitted earlier for award of any degree or diploma to the best of my knowledge and belief.

Name of the student; Tesfay Abraha _____ Signature date 6/26/2015

Name of the major supervisor Yassin Ibrahim (PhD) Signature date 6/26/2015

Name of Co-advisor Girma Gezimu Signature date 6/26/2015

Name of Chairman _____ Signature _____ date _____

Name of Internal Examiner _____ Signature _____ date _____

Name of External Examiner _____ Signature _____ date _____

6/26/2015

ABSTRACT

This research attempted to examine the Value Chain Analysis of Beef Cattle: The Case of Tahtay Koraro woreda Tigray, Ethiopia with the objective of assessing the linkage of actors between different participants, profit margin analysis, identify factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market and assessing the challenges and opportunities of beef cattle value chain. To do so, proportional sampling and simple random sampling techniques were employed. The totals of 130 households were selected for the study purpose. In line with this, a combination of data collection techniques with sample respondents, traders, inputs suppliers, butchers, hotels, individual consumers and focused group discussion were employed to gather qualitative and quantitative data. Descriptive statistics like frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviations and inferential statistics such as t-test and χ^2 -test were employed to see mean difference between and relationships of variables. Linear regression model was employed to identify factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market in the study area. The result shows that, from the total fourteen variables five of them show statistically difference with the quantity supply of beef cattle to the market at 1% and 10% level of significance namely; numbers of beef cattle owned, distance to main roads, access to credit service, access to market information and breed type. Beef cattle production serves as ample opportunity for increase beef cattle value chain activities. Though, good environmental condition for beef cattle production activities and freely purchasing and selling beef cattle. Some identified constraints were land, credit service, capital, reliable markets found very far, water constraints and lack of qualified market agent were occurred. The marketing costs and margins computation result of the study indicates that producers were highest beneficiary than other actors were connect to channels based on producer's share of final price. Therefore, the study concludes that, quantity supply of beef cattle to the market will be sustained through paying attention and moving along with those variables influencing quantity supply of beef cattle to the market significantly.

Key word: cattle, linear regression, Tabia, Tahtay Koraro, and Value Chain Analysis

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First I would like to extend my sincere gratitude and appreciation to my major advisor Dr. Yassin Ibrahim for his enthusiasm, and unreserved guidance, valuable comments, suggestions and also devoted much of his time in critically reading and commenting the manuscript starting from proposal to the end of the thesis, in spite of his busy schedule. My sincere gratitude also goes to my co-advisor Girma Gezimu (MSc) for his helpful suggestions and constructive comments starting from the proposal to the end of the study. Without their help, it would have not been possible to complete the study. Additionally, the institutional support from Aksum University is unforgettable.

I would like to extend my gratitude to my father, mother, brothers and sisters for their financial, moral and material support during my study.

I am also thankful to my friends Tsibuk Berhe, Gidey Beyene, for their cooperation during my stay in Aksum University Shire Campus is unforgettable. I would like to thank also to Ato Mokonen Embay Tahtay Koraro Woreda beef cattle experts and Woreda Office of Agriculture and Rural Development of the woreda coordinator for his support on collecting reliable data for the study with commitment and dedication and Ato Teklay Weldetnsae Shire Agricultural Technical Vocational Education and Training College for their material, financial and moral support during the implementation this research work. I am also grateful to farmers, friends and experts of Tahtay Koraro Woreda who were responded to all questions with patience and gave necessary information for this research work.

Finally, the Almighty of God in every step of my life and this thesis research work is unforgettable.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ACDI/VOCA	Agricultural Cooperative Development International and Volunteers in Overseas Cooperative Assistance
AGP	Agricultural Growth Programmed
BOANR	Bureau of Agricultural and Natural Resource
CSA	Central Statistical Authority
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
CMC	Cetral mixed crop livelihood zone
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GTP	Growth and Transformation Program
GIS	Geographical Information System
OLS	Ordinary Least of Square
HH	House Hold
KM	Kilometer
LMA	Livestock Marketing Authority
LMM	Livestock & Meat Marketing
NEPAD–CAADP	New Partnership for Africa’s Development – Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme
SPS	Sanitary and Phytosanitary Standards
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
TLU	Total Livestock Unit
VCA	Value Chain Analysis

LIST OF TABLES

Table1. 1: Description of dependent variables for analysis	27
Table1. 2: Description of independent variables for analysis	28
Table3. 1: Selected sampled house hold numbers from targeted Tabias	20
Table4. 1.Costs and margins of the actors selling beef cattle to butchers.....	39
Table4.2.Costs and margins of the actors selling beef cattle to butchers	39
Table4.3.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to Abergele	40
Table4.4. Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to consumers.....	40
Table4.5.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to hotel and restaurants.....	41
Table4.6.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to Abergele	41
Table4.7.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle from producers direct to Aberegele.....	42
Table4.8.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle from producers direct to butchers	42
Table4. 9. Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis of continuous variables	44
Table4. 10: Descriptive and Inferential Statistical Analysis of Categorical variables	45
Table4.11.Types of supplementary feed.....	47
Table4.12.Results of econometric model.....	50
Table4.13.challenges of beef cattle value chain	53
Table4. 14: Opportunity of beef cattle value chain.....	55

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure2. 1: Typical Structure of beef cattle markets in the study area	14
Figure3. 1: Location of study area.....	18
Figure3. 2: sampling procedure diagram	20
Figure4. 1: Input suppliers and their relationship with actors.....	29
Figure4. 2: Producers and their relationship with other beef cattle value chain actors	31
Figure4. 3: Collectors and their relationship with actors	32
Figure4. 4: Traders and their relationship with actors	33
Figure4. 5: Butchers and their relationship with actors	34
Figure4. 6: Hotels and restaurants relationship with actors	35
Figure4. 7: individual consumers and their relationship with actors	36
Figure4. 8: Abergele beef cattle exporters and their relationship with actors	37
Figure4. 9: Types of beef cattle	47

APPENDIX TABLE

Appendix table 1: Estimation of beef cattle in producers.....	83
Appendix table 2: Estimated costs for beef cattle in producers.....	84
Appendix table 3: Estimated costs for beef cattle in local collectors	85
Appendix table 4: Selling price of beef cattle in local collectors	86
Appendix table 5: Estimated costs for beef cattle marketing in traders	87
Appendix table 6: Selling price of beef cattle in traders.....	88
Appendix table 7: Estimated cost for beef cattle in butchers.....	89
Appendix table 8: Estimated cost of materials in butchers.....	90
Appendix table 9: selling price of beef cattle in butchers.....	91
Appendix table 10: Estimated price of beef cattle in hotels and restaurants	92
Appendix table 11: Estimated price of beef cattle in direct consumers.....	93
Appendix table 12: Estimated price of beef cattle in Aberegele	94
Appendix table 13: conversion factors of tropical livestock unit (TLU).....	94
Appendix table 14: Checking linearity of the model	95
Appendix table 15: Checking het-eroscedasticity and Homoscedasticity	95
Appendix table 16: Checking multi-collinarity using variance inflation factor for the continuous variables	96
Appendix table 17: checking multi-collinearity using contingency coefficient for categorical variable.....	96
Appendix table 18: mean difference between continuous variable using t=test value	97
Appendix table 19:chi-square test for categorical variables	97
Appendix table 20: sample size for determining population size	98
Appendix table 21: Sample photo during group discussion	99

TABLE OF CONTENT

DECLARATION	ii
ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	iv
LIST OF TABLES.....	v
LIST OF FIGURES	vi
APPENDIX TABLE.....	vii
TABLE OF CONTENT	viii
CHAPTER ONE	1
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Background.....	1
1.2. Statement of the problem.....	4
1.3. Objectives of the Study.....	5
1.3.1 General Objective	5
1.3.2. Specific Objectives	5
1.4. Research Questions.....	5
1.5. Hypothesis.....	5
1.6. Scope of the Study	6
1.7. Limitations of the Study.....	6
1.8. Significance of the Study.....	6
CHAPTER TWO	7
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	7
2.1. Value Chain Analysis of Beef Cattle Marketing	7
2.1.1. Concept of Value Chain Analysis.....	7
2.2 .Challenges and Opportunity of Beef Cattle Value Chain.....	9
2.2.1. Challenges of Beef Cattle Value Chain	9
2.2.2. Opportunity of Beef Cattle Value Chain	9

2.3. Factors Affecting Quantity Supply of Beef Cattle to the market.....	10
2.4. Market Linkage and Marketing Channels.....	11
1.5. Conceptual Framework of the Study.....	14
CHAPTER THREE	17
3. Research Methodology	17
3.1. Descriptions of the study area.....	17
3.2. Sampling Techniques.....	19
3.3. Method of Data Collection.....	21
3.4. Method of Data Analysis and Presentation.....	22
3.4.1. Econometric analysis	23
The contingency coefficients are computed as follows:.....	24
3.5. Definitions variables	25
3.5.1. Dependent Variables.....	25
3.5.2. Independent Variables	25
CHAPTER FOUR.....	29
4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION	29
4.1. Value Chain Analysis of Beef Cattle.....	29
4.1.1 .Actors in the Beef Cattle Value Chain and Their Relationship	29
4.1.3. Costs and margins among beef cattle marketing channels	38
4.2. Factors Affecting Quantity Supply of Beef Cattle to the Market	43
4.2.1. Descriptive results.....	43
4.3.2. Econometric Model Analysis.....	49
4.3.2.1. Econometric Model Out put.....	50
CHAPTER FIVE	56
5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	56
5.1 CONCLUSION.....	56
5.2. RECOMMENDATIONS	57
6. REFERENCES	58
7. APPENDIX.....	63

CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Livestock production is one of dominant part of Ethiopian agricultural sector. This sector contributes about 20%, 70% and 11% of GDP, to the livelihoods and generating annual export earnings, respectively. However, as it ranks first in Africa and tenth in the world, it has much to gain from the rising worldwide markets for livestock products (SPS-LMM, 2010).

Livestock marketing demand (LMD)'s value chain strategy will target market-focused actions that will generate demand, improve linkages, incentivize and create market relationships that encourage greater productivity, add value, and promote investment throughout the value chain (AGP, 2013).

(VCA) Value Chain Analysis studies on beef cattle enabled the identification of the major value chain actors and categorized as: input supplier, producers, traders, processors and consumers in order to know their relationship and characterize the beef activities focusing on constraints and opportunities (Addisu *et al.*, 2012).

Ethiopia earned income from beef cattle and this increased by market linkage activities of actors and opening of new markets. So in order to secure a sustainable quantity supply of beef cattle producers has prepared several ranches and fattening areas. Moreover, it plans to produce good quality of beef cattle by giving supplementary such as feed from oil cakes found from the two edible oil factories by mixing it with other ingredients such as wheat bran, middling, molasses and other additives (SPS-LMM, 2011).

Ethiopia has been unable to take the full advantage of improved access to foreign markets because of constraints that reduce quantity supply of beef cattle to the market and these constraints can be generalized as factors that inhibit production, marketing costs and poor infrastructure in most (FAO, 2005).

Ethiopia's domestic meat consumption for 2006/07 is estimated about 2.4 kg/capita/year for beef, and 0.7 and 0.4 kg/capita/year for sheep and goat meat, respectively. Pronounced differences have been identified between rural and urban patterns of meat consumption, particularly for beef about (1.7 versus 7.0 kg/capita/year respectively), (Sintayehu *et al.*, 2010).

Despite the prominence of cattle but only a small fraction of Ethiopian beef is raised in feedlots—the vast majority of cattle are fattened in backyard systems. So, its economy, qualitative and quantitative information is both scarce. Therefore meat that derived from culled draught oxen is a low-quality. Particularly, increased off take would enable encourage its value chain activities (Sintayehu *et al.*, 2013).

Beef cattle from the villages are normally trekked to the primary markets by their producers and sold to consumers or traders who move them to the larger markets and the places for beef cattle exchange can generally be divided into four types: (farm gate, primary market, secondary market and tertiary/terminal markets) and from this classification primary market serves as a collection ground for larger markets or a medium of farmers'. while secondary markets serve as a means of larger collection ground for export/ and supply of local bigger town consumers, the tertiary markets serve as supply of export markets or domestic meat producing industries and large butchereries (CSA, 2012).

It is a very well understood fact that Ethiopian farmers sell their beef cattle when they fail to cover their cash need from their crop enterprises and in such cases, farmers are forced to sell their beef cattle in special seasons of the year to repay their debt (input loan, tax, and other contributions) and to buy food for their household (Legese *et al.*, 2008).

Market information is essential for decision making in marketing, reducing transaction costs and business risks, facilitating the flow of goods from producers to consumers, meet consumer demands, and reduce cheating and unfair pricing practices (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2011).

Ethiopia is approximately self-sufficient in cattle, with surpluses primarily exported through informal channels but beef cattle production and marketing system as poorly productive, and cause of low off take is poor access to markets, market information and an apparent lack of understanding of what the market demands (Gebremariam *et al.*, 2013).

The beef cattle sub-sector in Ethiopia including Tigray region is an important and integral component of the agricultural sector. Beef cattle in the region are sources of cash income from sale of live animals and beef cattle products, food such as meat for household consumption (Gebremedhin *et al.*, 2007).

In Tigray, region beef cattle are valuable assets that are rarely sold, and hardly ever consumed. Beef cattle are kept as an asset that can provide relatively significant income in bad years. When beef cattle are sold, it should be at least three years after birth. Younger oxen are purchased from the market to replace old aged oxen. Mature females are scarcely available on the market. Beef cattle are exported to Axum from markets in Rama, Adwa, and Enticho coming from Edagaarbi (CMC, 2007).

Beef Cattle fattening in Tahtay Koraro Woreda are valuable components of the farming system contributing enormously to smallholder producers' livelihoods systems. There are quite large number of farmers engaged in small and medium scale fattening of cattle, with 2-3 fattening cycles/year with 120-150 days/cycle (SPS-LMM, 2010).

1.2. Statement of the problem

In Ethiopian, beef cattle value chains have developed into a series of complex involving various actors in order to sell in the world market. However, in Ethiopia, many producers only sell their beef cattle when they need the money or when a drought hits (AGP, 2013).

Beef cattle marketing system in Ethiopia is very complex, linking a number of different types of market actors as the marketed beef cattle move from producers to the end users. The different links in the process of such market chains indicate the different services that are provided to deliver the beef cattle to the various consumers (Addisu *et al.*, 2012).

Factors affecting quantity of beef cattle supplied to market were constrained when actors are not effective in delivering value added, limited transparency on quality, health, religious and cultural festivals and also due to weak linkages between actors (Sintayehu *et al.*, 2010).

Due to the low productivity of beef cattle and the absence of market-oriented production systems, the volume of marketed surplus is very low. Because, of the constraints in the market information, poor market infrastructures like road, seasonality in production. Thus, it is essential to identify the major factors contributing for the quantity supply shortage that has hindered smooth functioning of the Ethiopian beef cattle value chain activities (Legese *et al.*, 2008).

Farmers in Tigray reported that they get information informally from neighbors who visited the market some time before them, asking traders coming from towns, discussions during social gatherings in the community/village to which farmers have better trust. However, farmers do not seem to target these markets in terms of producing better beef cattle for selling. The price was probably exaggerated due to the poor quantity supply of beef cattle to the market and beef cattle producers in Tigray lack market orientation (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2011).

Moreover, numerous studies conducted so far in the field give more emphasis to the Southern Tigray (Alamata, Raya Azebo) and other regions in the country (Simeon *et al.*, 2007, Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009, SPS-LMM, 2010, SPS-LMM, 2011, Addisu *et al.*, 2013, Sintayehu,

2013). So far no studies have been conducted in the Tahatay Koraro woreda in this theme. Such partial assessments do not verify the value chain analysis of beef cattle in the country in general and Tigray in the particular. Since it requires area specific studies thus this research aims to analyze beef cattle value chain in Tahtay Koraro woreda.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

1.3.1 General Objective

The general objective of the study is to analyze beef cattle value chain in Tahtay Koraro Woreda, North-Western Zone Tigray

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of study were:

- To assess the linkage of actors between different participants
- To assess profit margin analysis between actors
- To identify factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market
- To assess the challenges and opportunities of beef cattle value chain

1.4. Research Questions

The study was tried to answer the following major questions:

1. what is the linkage of actors, profit margin and estimate the distribution of costs between different participants ?
2. What are the factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market?
3. What are the challenges and opportunities of beef cattle value chain?

1.5. Hypothesis

- Numbers of beef cattle owned is significantly affects its quantity supplied to market
- Access to market information is significantly associated with quantity supply of beef cattle to the market
- Access to credit service is significantly affects quantity supply of beef cattle to market

1.6. Scope of the Study

The study is limited to Tahtay Koraro Woreda to analyze beef cattle value chain at producer' level. This study is an individual survey on which representative sample size was selected by using both proportional and simple random sampling techniques.

1.7. Limitations of the Study

The study was focused on analyzing beef cattle value chain in Tahtay Koraro Woreda in its 13 Tabias while intending to use it at zonal and other higher administrative level were not administered due to time and budget constraints which may have its own limitation in representing all types of commodities of the study area.

1.8. Significance of the Study

Value chain analysis of beef cattle is an important focal point for achieving agricultural beef cattle product to the consumer. The study is also believed to enable agricultural extension institution and others to make the system to assess the value chain of beef cattle marketing in general and beef cattle value and marketing in particular and to tackle failure of their beef cattle value chain and marketing system by suggesting some practical measures to be undertaken by these owners in order to solve the number of problems faced, there by contributing to poverty reduction.

The study also provides base line information for other studies; that focus on similar topic and issues, related to value chain of beef cattle marketing particular and other commodities in general. In addition to this, the result may also be used for drawing logical and conceptual relationships among variables. The in-depth review of literatures in this topic, apart from enhancing and enriching the knowledge base of the researcher; is believed to be a basic document in the field that could further enable producers and different beef cattle traders at different level to see many dimensions and increase in the existing knowledge-based system of different agricultural related programs.

CHAPTER TWO

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Value Chain Analysis of Beef Cattle Marketing

2.1.1. Concept of Value Chain Analysis

Value chain analysis (VCA) has been defined as an integrated set of tools and processes that are used to define current costs and performance, as well as to assess the potential impact of consumer response improvement across the entire supply chain for consumer goods product categories. However, as VCA has matured, its tools have been expanded to include the assessment of consumer demand and on market share (Kaplinsky *et al.*, 2001).

In value chain analysis, vertical and horizontal integration are the two basic strategies that groups of farmers can use to improve their incomes in to vertical integration means taking on additional activities in the value chain: processing or grading produce. Horizontal integration on the other hand means becoming more involved in managing the value chain itself – by farmers' improving their access to and management of information, their knowledge of the market, their control over contracts, or their cooperation with other actors in the chain (KIT, 2006).

The analysis of a value chain stresses that the market is increasingly organized through networks linking spatially dispersed market agents. The outputs in the chain are determined by the requirements of the market agents including cost, value-added which are, in turn, responding to the demands of their customers (Dolan *et al*, 2000).

Ethiopia predominantly is agro-pastoral production system in the lowland and mixed crop livestock system in the highlands and central highlands. However, the production of beef cattle will remain low unless supported by intensive production system. There no strategic value chain of beef cattle marketing in Ethiopia except some sales targeted to traditional Ethiopian festivals (Alemayehu,2011).

There is lack of well-coordinated beef cattle marketing that links many producers and buyers and it's distributed through complex channel of marketing chains that involve a number of intermediaries and marketing agents, causing the system to be less efficient and traders want to hide information from the higher level markets to their own advantage (Legese *et al.*, 2008).

The performance of a market is influenced by the structural characteristics of the market and the competitive behavior of actors in the market's chain and dealing with these factors provide a basis for the formulation of interventions (William *et al.*, 2006).

The beef cattle marketing structure follows a four-tier system, of which different actors involve in buying and selling of beef cattle in the market system .The main actors of the 1st tier are local farmers and small traders from different corners bring their livestock to the local market (2nd tier).In the secondary market (3rd tier), both smaller and larger traders operate and traders and butchers from terminal markets come to buy animals. In the terminal market (4th tier), big traders and butchers transact larger number of mainly slaughter type animals (Yacob *et al.*, 2010).

2.2 .Challenges and Opportunity of Beef Cattle Value Chain

2.2.1. Challenges of Beef Cattle Value Chain

The major weaknesses of the traders involved in beef cattle value chain are capital shortage, limited access to credit, lack of experts as market agent mainly involved in periodical market assessment, low levels of education, unevenly distributed of market information, inadequate road network; unreliable, deficient and high cost feed supply; disease problem and lack of veterinary services (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009).

Limited access to market related information such as, prices, competitors, consumer preferences and lack of capital investment in assets, equipment and input that would improve quality are the major challenges faced by marketing. Beef cattle diseases, support services and infrastructure are very weak continue to limit Ethiopia's access to attractive markets (Workneh, 2006).

2.2.2. Opportunity of Beef Cattle Value Chain

High demands of beef cattle by the local abattoirs, increasing official exports and increasing domestic meat consumption are the opportunities that will enhance beef cattle value chain in Ethiopia plenty (Alemayehu, 2011).

Most Ethiopia butchers typically sold only cattle meat. Reasons for this are the selling price of meat showed increment from the past times, the export market and the increment of the local demand for the cattle meat enhanced the price of meat and rise of the local demand for beef (ACDI/VOCA, 2008).

When income of the producers increases through better access to information, market and infrastructure, they could improve production, both in terms of quantity and quality, there by benefiting consumers (Ayele *et al.*, 2003).

2.3. Factors Affecting Quantity Supply of Beef Cattle to the market

Despite the reported high livestock population of the country, the major constraints to be complex are beef cattle are complaining of shortage of quantity supply and inferior quality of beef cattle. The problem could be because of the constraints in the marketing system of beef cattle, the market information system, poor market infrastructures like road, lack of supplementary feed, and problems in the production system. Thus, it is essential to identify the major factors contributing for the low quantity supply of beef cattle to market and reduces non-value adding transaction costs among different actors (Legese *et al.*, 2008).

Transport cost from production areas to the center are the major cost components of marketing operations and analysis of the total marketing costs of each actors participating in different channels indicated that exporters have the highest costs, followed by feed lot operators, big traders, small traders and collectors (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009).

Transporting of beef cattle to markets and other final destinations is delicate and expensive and beef cattle could lose weight in transit or suffer injuries due to unstable means of transport. They are also exposed to disease-causing pathogens (NEPAD-CAADP, 2005).

Extension service is providing marketing advice, market information and linking farmers with markets of both inputs and outputs. In this regard, it is important that the extension service accords due attention to the development of the knowledge and skills of farmers, and facilitating their linkages with marketing and financial services. Hence, marketing and extension is crucial in quantity supply of beef cattle to the market (Yacob *et al.*, 2010).

2.4. Market Linkage and Marketing Channels

The analysis of beef cattle marketing channels is assumed to provide a systematic knowledge of the flow of livestock from their production areas to their final end-users. Marketing of beef cattle generally starts with the collection of livestock from production areas and village markets moving on to the terminal markets in the cities. In such marketing chains the livestock passes successively through a number of market actors, implying the links in the value chains before it reaches to the end-users (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009).

Conventionally many beef cattle markets in Ethiopia are categorized into primary market, secondary market and terminal market. In terms of market participant's primary markets are those in which the main sellers are producers and the main buyer's local assemblers and secondary markets are those in which the main sellers are local assemblers and main buyers are big traders. In terminal market the main sellers are traders and main buyers are butcheries and restaurants (Legese *et al.*, 2008).

Primary markets are markets where producers strongly dominate to sell beef cattle primarily to small-scale farmer and traders at market centers located in rural areas and *woreda* capitals. Primary markets have been identified as village level markets with a supply of less than 500 head of cattle/week. Supply of beef cattle to the primary, secondary and also the terminal markets is mostly done through trekking and trucking routes (Workneh, 2006).

The beef cattle market is structured so that the marketable beef cattle from the major producing areas reach to the final consumer or end-user passing through complex channels along the supply chains involving various actor including producers, middlemen, and meat exporters (Ayele *et al.*, 2003).

2.4.1. Distribution of Costs and Margins

Beef cattle marketing in Ethiopia are very complex, linking a number of different types of market actors as the marketed beef move from producers to the end users and different services that are provided to deliver the beef cattle to the various consumers. To clearly see the distribution of costs and margins among the actors, the marketing costs of beef cattle starting from the producers and the different end-users have been identified. At each stage of the chain, the value of the product increases as the product becomes more suitable for the end users. As a result, depending on the involvement of the market intermediaries in beef cattle marketing from the producer to the consumer, the following were observed to be the major marketing channels (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009).

Major marketing channels for beef cattle:

Channel 1: Producer → consumers

Channel 2: Producer → local Assembler → consumer

Channel 3: Producer → local Assembler → retailer → consumer

Channel 4: Producer → retailer → butcher → consumer

Channel 5: Producer → butcher → consumers According to (Ayele *et al.*, 2003).

This shows that, beyond transporting and limited fattening operation, relatively few market services are usually observed in the process. For our purpose, considering the overall structure of the system is quite complex, major marketing costs, each for cattle starting from the producers and the different end-users has been identified.

Net marketing margins of a particular marketing agent, as an indicative of the efficiency of the channel, is defined as the residual of the gross marketing margin after paying marketing costs (Mendoza, 1995 cited Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009). The following facts and assumptions are considered as the basis for estimating the cost and margins for the different beef cattle marketing channels as indicated below:

- Net marketing margins of a particular marketing agent as an indicator of the efficiency of the channel, is defined as the residual of the gross marketing margin after paying marketing costs. Hence, a net marketing margin is specified as:

Gross marketing margin = Selling price - Buying price

Net marketing margin = Gross Margin - Marketing cost

Marketing costs are composed of the total costs incurred on marketing of produce by each agent. It can be defined as the sum of charges paid for any marketing activity such as cost of transportation, and cost of capital invested in trading and transaction costs including fees paid to intermediaries, agents for entry and exit of animals, administrative charges as well as official and illicit taxes (Williams *et al.*, 2006).

The relative importance of these channels also varies as per the type of participants and customer objectives. Accordingly to Legese *et al.*, (2008) the major market participants of beef cattle trade includes producers, collectors, traders and butchers who carry out the various functions of the cattle market.

Producers: These are farmers producing cattle. Although these are the main source of marketed beef cattle, they are located in the rural areas where access to the market is very difficult and marketing information for the producers is very scarce.

Collectors: These are important market agents collecting beef cattle from their locality and remote markets and in most cases; these actors are independent operators who use their local knowledge and social relationships to collect beef cattle from the surrounding and other remote areas. In ILRI when they operate with the traders' money, the commission for their services is Birr 0.25–1.00 per kg live weight, in most of the cases and purchasing is done through “eye ball” negotiations and agreements. Most producers thus sell small number of beef cattle to traders in the nearby primary markets (Legese *et al.*, 2008).

Traders: The small traders in turn sell their beef cattle to big traders and/or exporters found in secondary larger markets. Such big traders and exporters are also reported to have better experience and financial performance in cattle trade and better access to relevant market information sources (Legese *et al.*, 2008).

1.5. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Value chains include input suppliers, producers, processors and buyers. They are supported by a range of technical, business and financial service providers (Kaplinsky *et al.*, 2001).

The performance of a market is influenced by the structural characteristics of the market and the competitive behavior of actors in the market's chain and dealing with these factors provide a basis for the formulation of interventions (William *et al.*, 2006).

The application of a value chain approach is proving fruitful in identifying the development potential of particular global industries and their prospects for broad based growth. Access to chain is influenced by wide range of level of infrastructure and access to technology, as well as the character of markets (Kaplinsky *et al.*, 2001).

Ethiopia has been unable to take the full advantage of improved access to foreign markets because of constraints in the domestic quantity of beef cattle supply. These constraints along the quantity supply of beef cattle can be generalized as factors that inhibit production, factors that increase marketing costs and those factors that reduce quantity supply of beef cattle (FAO, 2005).

Figure2. 1: Typical Structure of beef cattle markets in the study area

The independent variables in the conceptual frame work were selected after extensive literature review which shown that out of many other factors that affect quantity of beef cattle supply to the market were the most important and relevant ones. The frame work assumes that performance is a net result of the positive and negative effects exerted by all the explanatory variables on the dependent variable.

- Distance to the nearest beef cattle marketing (X1)
- Total number of beef cattle owned (X2)
- Age of the house hold head (X3)
- Sexes of house hold head (X4)
- Size of land holding (X5)
- Distance to the main road (X6)
- Education level of household head (X7)
- Extension service (X8)
- Credit access (X9)
- Market information (X10)
- Breed type (X11)
- Feed supplement (X12)
- Numbers of livestock producing (X13)
- Family size(14)

Figure2.2: interconnectedness of the different variables

The above figure indicates the conceptual framework of the study and the interconnectedness of the different variables. So, that based on the above figure the research was conducted. Conceptually, the study was focused on value chain analysis of beef cattle, all other commodities not to be administered in this study due to time and budget constraints.

CHAPTER THREE

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Descriptions of the study area

The study was conducted in Woreda Tahtay Koraro which is located at a distance of 320 km North West of Mekelle, the capital city of Tigray, and regional state. The average elevation of the area is approximately 1800 m.a.s.l with $14^{\circ} 06'$ to $14^{\circ} 07'$ N latitude and $38^{\circ} 16'$ to $38^{\circ} 17'$ East longitude and with an average range of temperature 25°C - 35°C and 700-900 mm of annual average range of rainfall (BoANR, 2013).

According to the Tigray Bureau of Agriculture and Natural Resources (BoANR, 2013), the study area does have a total area coverage of 66,954.42 hectares so, Economy of the Woreda is predominantly dependent on crop production followed by livestock production. Sorghum, maize, tef, and millet are the main crops produced in the area under rain fed condition. Vegetables and fruits are also produced in the Woreda under irrigation as well as under rain fed conditions. Bushes, shrubs and grasses are the main vegetation of the area and it covers about 17223.5 hectare. The woreda consists of different soil type as clay (73%), loam (25%) and sand (2%).

The topography of the study area is mainly flat and semi-flat which is covered by 70% and the remaining 30% belongs to mountain areas respectively (BoANR, 2013).

The study woreda is classified in to three agro ecological zones consisting 2% Dega (highlands), 75 % Woinadega (midlands) and 23 % Kola (low lands) respectively (BoANR, 2013).

Out of the total area coverage of the woreda (66,954.42), 29.5% is cultivated land, 27% used as grazing land and forest and area enclosures constitute 32%. The remaining 11.5% is waste land (BoANR 2013). Livestock plays a major role in crop production areas of the mid highlands and lowlands for cereal production (draught power) in addition to meat, milk and prestige values. The livestock resources of the woreda are 121; 862 cattle, 44; 916 sheep, 11; 2835 goats, 156915 poultry 9295 beehives, 9256 donkeys, 725 camels and 137 mules (BoANR 2010). Cereals such as maize, Tef, sorghum and millet are the important crops of the area. According to CSA (2013), the human population of the woreda is estimated to be 83,019. Out of them 40,853 are females and 42,166 are males.

Figure3. 1: Location of study area

Source: own map using GIS

3.2. Sampling Techniques

To achieve the main aims of this study both, proportionate and simple random sampling techniques were employed. To employ proportioned sample technique, first, Tahtay Koraro Woreda was purposively selected according to the homogeneity of the population in beef cattle production of the study. Secondly, all 13 *Tabias* of beef cattle producers were selected and a total of 100 respondents were selected. On the other hand, simple random sampling method was employed to select the households from selected *Tabias* based on similarity of the *Tabias* in terms of producing beef cattle. In addition, 30 respondents input suppliers, collectors, traders, butchers, hotels and individual consumers were selected using snowball techniques to share their idea through structured and semi-structured questionnaire and focusing group discussion.

For the study, single household had a chance of being selecting once at a time to collect unbiased data to achieve the objective of the study.

In principle, a number of factors determine the appropriate sample size that sufficiently represents the population. The decision on the selection of the method of sampling techniques depend on the objective of the study, information available about the target population before survey, the size of the target population and the natural order of the individuals in the study (Rengaswamy, 2007). According to James *et al.*, (2001) sample size of the population were determining from the given table using 5% tolerated error is the maximum sample size of the population were 100 number of house hold.

The sample households from each *Tabias* were determined by using proportionate sampling method to get representatives from each *Tabias* according to their size to get reliable data within the specific size. The households selected based on the formula of proportionate sampling which is:

$$nh = \frac{n}{N} * h$$

nh = sample taken from the stratum

n = population of the given stratum

N = total population of the each stratum

h = the total sample to be taken the given stratum (Kothari, 1990)

After determining the sample size from each *Tabias* respondents included in the study were selected by using simple random sampling to reduce biasness.

Table3. 1: Selected sampled house hold numbers from targeted *Tabias*

NO	<i>Tabias</i>	Number of house hold	Proportional Sampling taken from each house hold
.1	<i>Haftom/lemlem</i>	120	28
2.	<i>Laelayadigebaro</i>	59	13
3.	<i>Maydumu</i>	53	12
4.	<i>Taitayadigebaro</i>	24	5
5.	<i>May liham</i>	31	7
6.	<i>May adrasha</i>	30	7
7.	<i>Beles</i>	35	8
8.	<i>Adimenabr</i>	37	8
9.	<i>Semema</i>	8	2
10.	<i>Koyetsa</i>	12	3
11.	<i>Adigdad</i>	8	2
12.	<i>Kelakil</i>	9	2
13.	<i>Adikokeb</i>	13	3
<i>Total</i>		439	100

Source: (BoANR, 2013)

Table 1 indicates that the sample households were selected using proportionate sampling method to get reliable sample size for a given population of the *Tabias* selected for the study. The total households which were selected for the study were 100 samples household with equal size from each *Tabias* to get reliable data on the value chain analysis of beef cattle.

Figure3. 2: sampling procedure diagram

Source: Researcher's own sampling design, 2015

3.3. Method of Data Collection

The data collected from both primary and secondary data sources were qualitative and quantitative in nature. Primary data was collected through semi-structured questionnaire, focus group discussion making and interview from sample households and with beef cattle experts using questionnaire and checklist were used as data collection tools to get information about the farmers perception, respondent and the factors affecting quantity of beef cattle supply to the market, assessment of linkage of actors and estimation of market margin and marketing channel in the study area.

Before the administration of the semi-structured interview schedules, the respondents were informed about the objectives of the survey. The interview schedule was pre-tested using non-sample respondents before actual data collection and amendments were made accordingly. Local enumerators were recruited and trained to administer the interview under close supervision of the researcher. During the interview, the researchers as well as respective trained enumerators' were collected enough information for achieving the objectives of the study to avoid potential bias from the sample households in responding questions. Information generated through semi-structured questionnaire was supplemented by focusing group discussion with the local people to get the reliability of the data collected regarding to the objective of the study in the woreda.

3.4. Method of Data Analysis and Presentation

The collected data was analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics as well as linear regression econometric model. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, standard deviation and percentages as well as inferential statistics like chi-square and t-test were employed.

Moreover, the data on the factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market was analyzed using OLS model. To do so, statistical packages like SPSS version 20 and STATA version 10 were employed.

Marketing margin: The marketing margin is a measure of the percentage of price that is paid by the consumer that is maintained by each agent in the marketing chain. These include the total gross marketing margin, producer's gross marketing margin, and net marketing margin. These margins was calculated by deducting the selling price and marketing cost from the purchased price and then dividing by the price paid by the end users and the proportion and distribution of these values among marketing actors was be used to study the performance of village beef cattle marketing system (Mendoza, 1995). The margins were calculated using the following equation as follows:

$$TGMM = \frac{\text{Endbuyerprice} - \text{firstsellerprice}}{\text{endbuyerprice}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, TGMM = Total gross marketing margin

$$GMMP = \frac{\text{Endbuyerprice} - \text{marketinggrossmargin}}{\text{endbuyerprice}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where, GMMP = the producer's marketing margins (producers share) from consumer price.

$$NMM = \frac{\text{Grossmargin} - \text{marketingcosts}}{\text{endbuyerprice}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where, NMM = Net marketing margin

Hence, a net marketing margin is specified as:

Gross marketing margin = Selling price - Buying price

Net marketing margin = Gross Margin - Marketing Costs

Marketing costs are composed of the total costs incurred on marketing of produce by each agent. It can be defined as the sum of charges paid for any marketing activity such as cost of transportation, and cost of capital invested in trading and transaction costs including fees paid to

intermediaries, agents for entry and exit of animals, administrative charges as well as official and illicit taxes (Williams *et al*, 2006).

Market cost: This includes handling, loading and unloading cost), transportation cost, production loss, capital cost, commission and other unofficial payments. The various institutions involved in beef cattle market system and their role was identified using information from informal survey. Furthermore, the different market channels and the percentage share of these channels were identified. The result of this market investigation was compared with the perfectly competitive market conditions to measure the marketing efficiency.

3.4.1. Econometric analysis

In order to identify factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to market, the linear regression econometric model was employed. Because, dependant variable is a continuous and its value is known. On the other hand, the OLS method is used to estimate the parameters of the model and determines those values of β_0 (constant) and β_i (coefficients of explanatory variables), which minimize the sum of squared deviation of the observed values Y_i (dependent) from the predicted values.

Linear regression models are fit between independent variables (X_i) also called regressor or predictors and the dependent variable (Y) also called response variable or predicted variable. If the response variable (y) is only dependent on a single independent variable (x), the fitted equation is called simple linear regression model. According to Gujarati (2004) the linear regression model specified as follows:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \dots + \beta_n X_n + U_i \dots\dots\dots (4) \text{ Where, } \beta_1 = \text{Regression coefficient representing the slope the line, } \beta_0 = \text{intercept, when } x = 0, X = \text{explanatory variables and } U_i = \text{error term}$$

Estimation procedure

Before estimating model parameters, it would be necessary to check whether there is multi collinearity among the continuous variables and verify the degree of association among discrete variables. The reason is that if the existence of multi collinearity turns out to be significant, the simultaneous presence of the two variables will attenuate or reinforce the individual effect of these variables. However, omitting an important independent variable that has statistically

significant influence on the dependent variable will lead to a specification bias. The coefficients of the interaction of the variables indicate whether or not one of the two associated variables should be eliminated from model analysis (Kothari, 1990).

Gujarat (2004) denoted that there are various indicators of multi collinearity and no single diagnostic will give us a complete handle over the collinearity problem. Among the various indicators of multi collinearity, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is used in this study to check whether there is multi collinearity or not among the continuous explanatory variables. In this method, each continuous explanatory variable has been regressed on others and coefficients of determination for each axillaries or subsidiary regression computed. In addition, Gujarat (2004) stated that a high R^2 obtained could only be a surface indicator of multi collinearity. Therefore, a measure of multi collinearity associated with the variance inflation factors is defined as:

$$\text{VIF} (X_j) = \left(\frac{1}{1 - R_j^2} \right) \dots\dots\dots 5$$

Where:

X_j = the j th quantitative explanatory variable regressed on the other quantitative explanatory variables.

R_j^2 = the coefficient of determination when the variable X_j regressed on the remaining explanatory variables.

As a rule of thumb, if the VIF of a variable exceeds 10 that variable is said to be highly collinear and it can be concluded that multi collinearity is a problem (Gujarat, 2004). It is also evident that there might be interaction among qualitative variables, which could lead to the problem of multi collinearity. To detect this problem, contingency coefficients were computed for each pair of qualitative variables.

The contingency coefficients are computed as follows:

$$C = \sqrt{\frac{X^2}{n + X^2}} \dots\dots\dots 6$$

Where, C= coefficient of contingency, X^2 = a Chi-square random variable and n = total sample size.

3.5. Definitions variables

This part of the study was tried to hypothesize factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market. In the course of identifying factors influencing quantity supply of beef cattle to the market, the main task is to explore which factors potentially influence and how (the direction of the relationship) these factors related with the dependent variables. Therefore, potential variables, which are supposed to influence quantity supply of beef cattle to market, were explained. Thus the lists of variables were expected to have influence on both the farmers' participation decision and volume of quantity supplied to markets was defined.

3.5.1. Dependent Variables

Quantity of beef cattle supplied (QUTBSPLD): It is a continuous variable which represents the quantity of beef cattle supply to the market by beef cattle producers of the sample respondents.

3.5.2. Independent Variables

Number of livestock producing stock (NULPS): It is continuous variable and marginal increase in beef cattle production has obvious and it is expected to have significant effect on quantity of beef cattle supply. As the number of dairy cow increases, production beef cattle also increases so, it is expected to have a positive effect on the sales of beef cattle.

Distance to the nearest beef cattle market (DSTBEFCMKT): It is a continuous variable measured in km which the farmer spends to reach the nearest beef cattle market. If the farmer is located in a village that is further distant from the market place, he/she is poorly accessible to the market. The closer the market place the lesser could have transportation cost and time spent. Therefore, it is hypothesized that this variable is negatively related to sales quantity of beef cattle.

Total number of beef cattle owned (TNBRDOWN): It is a continuous variable and measured by the number of beef cattle kept by producer during the survey period. A marginal increase in beef cattle production is expected to have significant effect on the quantity of beef cattle supply to market. Quantity of beef cattle production is expected to have positive relationship with supply of beef cattle to market.

Age of the household head (AGHHD): It is a continuous variable and measured in the age (years) of the household heads. This variable is expected to have negative relationship with the quantity supply to market.

Sex of the household head (SEHH): This is dummy variable (takes a value of 1 if the household head is male and 0 otherwise). In this study, if female participation is expected to affect quantity of beef cattle supply is positive

Family size (FAMSIZ): It is a continuous variable, measured in the total number of the household, which affects farmer's decisions to supply quantity of beef cattle to market. Any family member might decide to participate in beef cattle marketing. Hence it is expected to have positive and negative relationship.

Size of land holding (LNDHLD): This is the total land holding measured in hectare, which is a continuous variable and expected to have positive relationship with beef cattle quantity of supply to market. If the producer has large land size the probability of the amount of quantity of beef cattle supply is expected to be high.

Education level of household head (EDUCHHD): It is a categorical variable and refers to the household head of education level. Those household heads who have formal education determines the readiness to accept new ideas and innovations, and hence promote to get supply, demand and price information and this enhances farmers' willingness to participate in quantity supply of beef cattle to market and increase volume of sale. Therefore, education level is expected to have positively relationship with quantity supply of beef cattle to market.

Extension service (EXTSRV): A dummy variable measured in access to extension workers for beef cattle marketing assuming extension service as a source of information on the marketing of beef cattle under consideration. Farmers who have access to extension workers are more likely to know the advantage of production like beef cattle and the availability, quality, and price of inputs and assigned with frequently and sometimes or not. Therefore access to extension agent is assumed to have positive relationship with quantity of beef cattle supply to market.

Credit access (CRDTACS): This is a dummy variable and measured with 1 for those farmers who take credit for the marketing of beef cattle and 0, otherwise. Access to credit could enhance the financial capacity of the farmers to purchase the necessary inputs for the marketing of beef cattle. Therefore, it hypothesized that credit have positive relationship with quantity supply of beef cattle to market.

Market information (MRKTINF): It is a dummy variable and assigned with 1 for those households who access marketing information and 0, otherwise. Farmers marketing decisions were based on market price, supply and demand information, and poorly integrated markets might convey inaccurate and inadequate information on price, demand and supply, leading to inefficient marketing decisions. Therefore, it hypothesized that market information has positive relationship with quantity supply of beef cattle to market.

Breed type (BT): This variable is a categorical variable indicating the breed type of the beef cattle that the household owned exotic, local and mixed breed. The former type is more productive in terms of meat yield. But due to feed requirement and disease vulnerability farmers may prefer the local breed type. Therefore, this variable might take both negative and positive sign on quantity of beef cattle to market.

Feed supplement (FS): It is a dummy variable and assigned 1 for those farm households who supplement feed for their beef cattle and 0, otherwise. Feed supplementations for local beef cattle would significantly improve the productivity of local breeds. Thus, this variable is expected to positively affect.

Distance to main road (DSTMR): It is a continuous variable measured in km which the farmer spends to reach the main road. If the farmer is located further distant from the main road, he/she is poorly accessible to the main road. The closer the main road place the lesser could have transportation cost and time spent. Therefore, it is hypothesized that this variable is negatively related to sales quantity of beef cattle.

Table1. 1: Description of dependent variables for analysis

No	Variables	Unit of measurement	Definition of variable	Expected sign
1	VQUTSPLD	Number	quantity of beef cattle supplied	+

Table1. 2: Description of independent variables for analysis

No	Variables code	Unit of measurement	Definition of variable	Expected sign
1	NULPS	Number	Number of livestock producing stock	+
2	DSTNMKT	Km	Distance to the nearest beef cattle market	-
3	TNBRDOWN	Number	Total number of beef cattle owned	+
4	AGHHD	Years	Age of the household head	-
5	SEHH	Dummy	Gender of the household head	+
6	FAMSIZ	Number	Family size	-/+
7	LNDHLD	Hectare	Size of land holding	+
8	EDUCHHD	Category	Education level of household head	+
9	EXTSRV	Dummy	Extension service	+
10	CRDTACS	Dummy	Credit access	+
11	MRKTINF	Dummy	Market information	+
12	BT	Category	Breed type	-/+
13	FS	Dummy	Feed supplement	+
14	DSTMRTKT	Km	Distant to the main road	-

CHAPTER FOUR

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the overall findings of the study under different sections and sub sections. The descriptive analysis of beef cattle value chain like profit margin of actors, the relationship between actors, and factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market, challenges and opportunities of beef cattle value chain are discussed below.

4.1. Value Chain Analysis of Beef Cattle

4.1.1 .Actors in the Beef Cattle Value Chain and Their Relationship

The major actors in the beef cattle value chain in the study areas were input suppliers, producers, local collectors, traders, butchers, hotels and individual consumers. This results is in line with (Addisu *et al.*, 2012), on similar study mention this study area. The relationships between each of the actors with their constraints were presented as follows:

I. Input suppliers and their relationship with beef cattle value chain actors

Source: own survey, 2015

Figure4. 1: Input suppliers and their relationship with actors

According to the survey result, 60% of beef cattle inputs were supplied by woreda agricultural office whereas 40% were supplied by other local traders in the study area. Regarding to relationship with beef cattle actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants) about 80% of respondents said that there is strong relationship among beef cattle value chain actors where as 20% responded that there is weak relationship among actors. Though 60% of inputs were supplied from government offices, 100% of surveyed households responded that there was weak relationship among government (input sender and price establisher) and other beef cattle value chain actors. Almost all surveyed respondents said that the main constraints for the relationship between beef cattle value chain are weak market linkage, lack or shortage of knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation. While, about 80% responded that lack of infrastructures are main constraints for strengthening their relationship with other beef cattle value chain actors in the study area. This implies that market information, actors' skill, attitude, motivation and access to infrastructures are important factor to strengthen the relationship among different actors in the beef cattle value chain in the study area.

II. Producers and their relationship with value chain actors

Source: own survey, 2015

Figure4. 2: Producers and their relationship with other beef cattle value chain actors

According to the survey result from the total sampled respondents about 1%, responded that the relationship between actors in the beef cattle value chain was strong while 81% responded that the relationship with beef cattle actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers) was weak. Further, about 50% sampled producers responded that there was weak relation between government(input sender and price establisher authority) and them regarding to beef cattle value chain while 48% responded that their linkage with government regarding beef cattle was weak. This indicated there is no formal linkage among the actors. Due to this fattened beef cattle could not be sold at the right time and incurs additional expenses. The study also indicated that about 63% respondents purchased their beef

from market whereas 37% and 8% of respondents purchased from producers, and traders respectively.

According to survey about 81%, 41% and 40 % purchaser of beef cattle from producers were butchers, traders and consumers respectively. However, local traders cover only 17% of supplied beef cattle in the study area. This results is in line with (Ayele *et al*, 2003), on similar study mention this study area.

About 98%, 12% and 55% of respondents said that the main factors constraining the linkages among beef cattle value chain actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers) and governments(input sender and price establisher authority) were market linkage, infrastructure and KSA (knowledge, skill, and attitude) and motivation respectively. As a result, those constraints are mainly due to weak market linkage among beef cattle producer and the actors

III. Local Collectors and Their Relationship with Value Chain Actors

Figure4. 3: Collectors and their relationship with actors

Source: own survey, 2015

As we it can be seen from figure 4.3 source of beef cattle for local collectors purchased were town market, producers in local market, such as *Mia hanse, Asgedetsibla, Sheraro, Tekeze and Laelayadiabo*. These areas were preferred because cattle from these areas have high supply. In addition, local collectors sold their beef cattle to butchers (100%), other local consumer (80%) and traders (20%). Regarding, relationship with other beef cattle actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers) about 20 and 40 percents of local traders responded that there were strong and weak relationship with them and other beef cattle value chain actors in the study area. While about 60 and 40 percents of them responded that their relationship with government (input sender and price establisher authority) concerning to beef cattle value chain is strong and weak respectively. However about 60% and 40% of sample collectors responded that relation with government were strong and weak respectively. Once more, the main factors constraining the linkage among beef cattle value chain actors and governments with collectors were market linkage (100%), infrastructure (20%) and KSA (knowledge, skill, and attitude) (100%) and motivation.

IV. Traders and their Relationship with Value Chain Actors

Figure4. 4: Traders and their relationship with actors
Source: own survey, 2015

The above figure shows that about 20%, 80% and 100% of traders have purchased their beef cattle from producers, local collectors and town market respectively. From the total sampled household about 20% respondents sold their beef cattle to local consumers and Aberegele to each. But, during Christmas, Muslims celebration and January period 100% of respondents sold their beef cattle to butchers. Most of the traders were preferred to buy from Western Sheraro, from local market, from town market, from producers, from *Kisad Gaba, Laelay Adigebaro Sheraro, Mai-Gaba, Mai-Hanse, Asgedetsibla* and from traders. Traders preferred to purchase from these areas largely because of high supply. 100% of traders responded that there was strong relationship among beef cattle actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers). While, about 40% and 60% of traders responded that their relationship with the government was strong and weak respectively. The main factors constraining the linkage traders with governments (input sender and price establisher authority) were policy, market linkage and KSA (knowledge, skill, and attitude) and motivation.

V. Butchers and Their Relationship with Beef Cattle Actors

Figure4. 5: Butchers and their relationship with actors

Source: own survey, 2015

The survey results in the above figure indicated that from the total butcher's about 60 % were purchased their beef cattle from traders' where as about 40 % purchased from market and most butchers preferred to purchase from those actors. This is possible because there were clear information between them. Finally butchers were selling raw meat and cooked meat to the final consumers'. From the total responded butchers about 20 % responded that there was good relationship among beef cattle value chain actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers) where as 80% of respondents said weak relationship respectively. However, about 80% and 20% said relationship with government (input sender and price establisher authority) was weak and good respectively. About 100% and 20% of respondents said that the main factors constraining the linkage among beef cattle value chain actors and governments were market linkage and KSA (knowledge, skill, and attitude) and motivation.

VI. Hotels and Restaurants and their Relationship with Value Chain Actors

Source: own survey, 2015

Figure4. 6: Hotels and restaurants relationship with actors

The above figure showed that from the total sampled house hold about 100% of hotels and restaurants responded that most of the time their beef cattle were purchased from town market and from regular suppliers of traders. Regarding to relationship with value chain actors about 100% of hotels and restaurants responded that there was weak relationship with beef cattle actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers). Likewise, about 100% responded that there was weak relationship with government (input sender and price establisher authority). Moreover, according to 100% sampled household responded that factors constraining the linkage among beef cattle value chain actors and government were market linkage and KSA (knowledge, skill, and attitude) and motivation.

VII. Individual consumers and their relationship with actors

Figure4. 7: individual consumers and their relationship with actors

Source: own survey, 2015

The figure 4.6 indicates that 100 % of sample respondents were purchased their beef from butcher while about 80% were purchased from traders, Collectors, local market and producers

respectively. This implies that, almost all sampled consumers were preferred to purchase beef cattle from butchers. .

About 60 % and 40% of sample house hold said there were weak and strong relationships with beef cattle actors respectively. Whereas, about 100% of individual consumers said that there was weak relationship beef cattle actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers) and government (input sender and price establisher authority) in the study area. On the other hand, factors constraining the linkage among beef cattle value chain actors were market linkage and KSA (knowledge, skill, and attitude) and motivation.

VIII. Aberegele exporters and their Relationship with Actors

Source: own survey, 2015

Figure4. 8: Aberegele beef cattle exporters and their relationship with actors

According to survey result from the total sampled respondents of Aberegele export 100% of its beef cattle was purchased from traders and producers respectively. This result showed that Aberegele purchased their beef cattle from traders and near local market such as MaiHanse, Asgedetsibla, Sheraro, Tekeze, Laelayadiabo, from Humera livestock ranching area. Because, in

this area are potential source of beef cattle supply. On the other hand, Aberegele international livestock exporters were sold their beef meat to Trans-Ethiopia, Mesobo-Cement and Exports to foreign country respectively. But, Aberegele were not obtaining sufficient amount of beef cattle because, most of the time foreign market requires beef cattle that are below age of five years so that they did not get sufficient number of stated age beef cattle due to this in the last a few times Aberegele international livestock exports not operating functionally but currently it is working its activities. Regarding to relationship with beef cattle actors (producers, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele and individual consumers) as the respondents said that there was strong relationship between them. However, about 100% of sample respondents said that relationship with government (input sender and price establisher authority) was weak. In the study area, the factors constraining the linkage between governments with Aberegele were market linkage (100%) and lack of KSA (knowledge, skill, and attitude) and motivation (100%).

4.1.3. Costs and margins among beef cattle marketing channels

Market channels in the study area were created a series of links from the producers and input suppliers up to the final consumers with different market cost through those channels. As it was discussed in section 4.1.2 the main actors in the study area were producers, local collectors, traders, butchers, hotels, restaurants and direct consumers. In the study area there were different market participation and distribution of marketing costs and margin among those actors. There were seven major market channels for beef cattle produced in study area and moving to the different terminal markets. This results is in line with (Addisu *et al.*, 2012) and (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009), on similar study in other study area. Based on cost benefit analysis from collected data of the study area, the analysis of marketing, costs and margins were estimated for the different beef cattle marketing channels as indicated below:

- Channel I: producers → local collectors → traders → butchers
- Channel -II: producers → traders → butchers
- Channel -III: producers → local collectors → traders → Aberegele (exports)
- Channel -IV: producer's → consumers
- Channel V: producer's → hotels and restaurants
- Channel VI: producers → local collectors → Aberegele
- Channel VII: producers → Aberegele
- Channel VIII: producers → Butchers

As the beef cattle are transferred through various marketing agents, the marketing costs incurred in these chains accumulate and finally determine the price in consumer markets table (4.3 -4.10)

Channel I: producers - local collectors – traders - butchers

Table4. 1.Costs and margins of the actors selling beef cattle to butchers

Criteria	Producers	Local collectors	Traders	Butchers
Selling price	6285	7720.96	8452	10046.079
Marketing cost	730.02	460	288.23	646.3436
Gross margin	4452.85	1435.96	731.04	1594.079
Net margin	3722.8	975.96	443	947.7354
Producer's share of final price (%)	62.56	14.3	7.23	15.86

Source: own survey 2015

From the above table 4.1 indicated that average selling price of beef cattle were increased from producers to butchers. Based on cost benefit analysis and the analysis of marketing cost, gross marketing margin, net margin and producers' share of final price and distribution of costs and margins among the beef cattle actors starting from the producers and the different end-users were different.

Channel two-II: producers – traders- butchers

Table4.2.Costs and margins of the actors selling beef cattle to butchers

Criteria	Producers	Traders	Butcher
Selling price	6747.368	8732.158	10117.125
Marketing cost	780.02	288.231	646.3436
Gross margin	4747.368	1984.788	1384.967
Net margin	3967.348	1696.556	738.621
Producer's share of final price (%)	66.69	19.62	13.7

Source: own survey 2015

From the table 4.2 the class of beef cattle in producers, traders and butcher were different in selling price, marketing cost, gross marketing margin, net margin and producer's share of final price due to the involvement of different marketing agents and costs. Accordingly, their margins

were different. But, selling price of beef cattle from producers to butchers showed an increasing trend.

Channel -III: producers –local collectors – Traders – Abergele (exports)

Table4.3.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to Abergele

Criteria	Producers	Local collectors	Traders	Abergele
Selling price	6429.03	6747.36	6922	8696.2
Marketing cost	730.02	199.19	100	628.556
Gross margin	4596.89	318.33	174.632	2850
Net margin	3866.87	119.13	74.632	1145
Producer's share of final price (%)	73.92	4	2	20.40

Source: own survey 2015

Table 4.3 showed that selling price, marketing cost, gross marketing margin, net margin and producer's share of final price of beef cattle in local collectors, traders and Abergele is different due to the difference in marketing agents that undertake the marketing activities, their cost components, prices and margins also differ. But, producers were preferred to sell their beef cattle in this channel next to channel VI. Because, producers share of final price were highest in this channel.

Channel -IV: producers – consumers

Table4.4. Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to consumers

Criteria	Producers	Direct Consumer
Selling price	6285	6285
Marketing cost	730.02	0
Gross margin	4452.85	0
Net margin	3722.8	0
Producer's share of final price (%)	100%	0

Source: own survey 2015

From the above table 4.4 selling price, marketing cost, gross marketing margin, net margin and producers share of final price marketing were differ due to the difference in cost of labor, house

rent and associated costs. But, most producers were preferred this channel to sell their beef cattle to direct consumers. Because, producers share of final price were highest in this channel.

Channel V: producers – butchers-hotel and restaurants

Table4.5.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to hotel and restaurants

Criteria	Producers	Hotel and restaurants
Selling price	7573.2	10589
Marketing cost	780.02	1696.8
Gross margin	5741.15	3015.8
Net margin	4961.1	1319
Producer's share of final price (%)	71.5	28.5

Source: own survey 2015

The above table 4.5 indicated that the difference in marketing costs, marketing margin and producers' share of final price were due to difference their mode of processing and associated cost of labor, house rent and marketing costs.

Channel VI: producers –small traders –Abergele

Table4.6.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle to Abergele

Criteria	Producers	local collectors	Abergele
Selling price	6429	7720.96	8696.2
Marketing cost	730.02	460	628.555
Gross margin	4596.89	1291.93	975.24
Net margin	3866.87	831.93	346
Producer's share of final price (%)	73.92	14.85	11.21

Source: own survey 2015

According to the above Table4.6 distribution of costs and margins among the beef cattle actors, the marketing, costs of beef cattle starting from the producers up to end-users of Aberegele were different. But, producers were preferred this channel next to channel IV. Because, producers share of final price were highest in this channel. So, it is easiest channel to sell their beef cattle in this channel.

Channel: producers –Aberegele

Table4.7.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle from producers direct to Aberegele

Criteria	Producers	Aberegele
Selling price	6922.15	9481.01
Marketing cost	780.02	1753.556
Gross margin	5090.01	2558.8626
Net margin	4309.99	805
Producers share of final price (%)	73.01	26.98

Source: own survey 2015

According to Table 4.7 the difference in marketing costs and marketing margin between the producers and Aberegele is because of their difference in associated costs such as: cost of labor, house rent and marketing agents that undertake the marketing activities, their cost components, prices and margins and producer’s share of final price also different.

Table4.8.Costs and margins of actors selling beef cattle from producers direct to butchers

Criteria	producers	Butchers
Selling price	6855.9	10046.079
Marketing cost	780.02	1876.2114
Gross margin	5023.9	3190.132
Net margin	4243.88	1313.9
Producer's share of final price (%)	68%	32%

Source: own survey 2015

From the above table (4.1 - 4.8) marketing of beef cattle in producers, local collectors, trader’s butchers, hotels and restaurants and Aberegele were different due to the difference in marketing agents that undertake the marketing activities, their cost components, prices, margins and % of producer’s share of final price.

Beef cattle which are fattened by farmer’s and average of their beef cattle age were ranges from 6-8 years old and sold their beef cattle though visual observation or eyeball techniques. While, Aberegele were sold their beef cattle based on their body weight. Body weight of their

beef cattle were about 400 (maximum), 340 (medium) and 270 (minimum) and established the price ranking methods based on this body weight respectively.

The actors of beef cattle marketed under different channels involved differ from the rest of marketing chains described above from table 4.1 - 4.8. The breed of animals that qualified for this class and the retail butcher's shops and customers involved were different from the channels described above. The animals most qualified for this category come from areas like: Kisadgaba, Dansha, Tekeze and Asgedetsimbla rarely from finisher commercial feedlots. The marketing cost for these marketing channels described here and it is attributed mainly to the cost of labor, house rent and associated costs. So, from this most producers were preferred to sell their beef cattle to direct consumers (Channel -IV: producers – consumers). Because, producers share of final price were highest in this channel and next to that channel producers were preferred to sell their beef cattle to Channel VI: producers –local collectors –Abergele and Channel -III: producers –local collectors –large traders – Abergel (exports).

4.2. Factors Affecting Quantity Supply of Beef Cattle to the Market

4.2.1. Descriptive results

This section shows the explanatory variables which influences the quantity supply of beef cattle to the market. They include: age of respondents, distance to the main roads, distance to nearest market, family size, landholding, livestock holding, sex of respondent, education level, access to credit service, numbers of beef cattle owned, access to extension service and access to market information, breed type and supplementary feed. As indicated in Table 4.9, the descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviations as well as the probability levels of all explanatory variables were used to analyze and interpret the data. Additionally, the detail relationships of those statistically significant explanatory variables with the quantity supply of beef cattle to the market were described as follows: In the following table, T-tests for continuous, and chi-square tests (χ^2) for dummy explanatory variables were used to examine data for differences, associations and relationships of variables.

Table4. 9. Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis of continuous variables

N	Variable	Descriptive statistics		t-value
		Mean	SD	
1.	AGHHD	40.73	7.765	52.451
2.	FAMSIZ	6.24	2.392	27.396
3.	LNDHLD	0.675	0.3295	20.491
4.	NULPS	6.33	2.704	23.406
5.	TNBROWN	2.87	1.060	27.067
6.	DSTNMK T	15	41.675	3.599
7.	DSTMRMKT	10	8.865	11.280

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Table 4. 10: Descriptive and Inferential Statistical Analysis of Categorical variables

Variable	Description	Frequency	%	Total	x ² -value
		N	%	%	
SEHH	Female	7	7	7	8.561
	Male	93	93	93	
BT	Local breed	98	98%	98	103.571
	Exotic	2	2%	2	
EDUCHHD	Illiterate	26	26	26	24.725
	1-4 grade	11	11	11	
	5-8 grade	40	40	40	
	9-10 grade	18	18	18	
	11-12 grade	5	5	5	
FS	Yes	84	84	84	5.432
	No	16	16	16	
CRDTACS	Yes	94	94	94	18.614
	No	6	6	6	
EXTSRV	Yes	55	55	55	20.159
	No	45	45	45	
MRKTINF	Yes	71	71	71	12.265
	No	29	29	29	

Source: Computed from own survey, 2015

Sex of the house hold (SEHH): Sex of the house hold is one of a potential factor which limits the quantity supply of beef cattle to the market. Due to the prevailing socio-cultural values and norms males have freedom of mobility, participate in different meetings and trainings. As result, males have more access of market information than female-headed households, which have a capacity to influence by the cultural norms and traditions. According to study result, from the total respondents, 93% and 7% of the sample house hold were male and female-headed

households respectively. So, there were a different between male and female with quantity of beef cattle supply to the market at χ^2 -value =8.561.

Educational level of the households head (EDUCHHD): The interviewed respondents were from different educational backgrounds. Accordingly, from the total sample households selected for the study, about 11% and 40%, of respondents were found in the educational level of grade 1-4 and 5-8 levels respectively. Whereas, about 18% and 5% were 9-10 grade and 11-12 grade. However, about 26% of respondents were from illiterate educational background.

Thus, the study result indicated that, among education level of sample households there were difference with χ^2 -value =24.725.

Age of house hold head (AGHHD): As shown in table 4.9, the average age of the sampled respondent in the study area was 40.73 years with standard deviation of 7.7 years. This implies that age composition of household in the study area were fail in the productive age group with age variation of 7.7 years from minimum to maximum age. Therefore, there were mean difference among age of the house hold with $t=52.451$.

Numbers of family size (FAMSIZ): In the study area availability of numbers of family size in the household is considered as the number of individuals who resides in the respondent's house hold. The average number of family size of total sample households in the study area was 6.24. Hence, there were mean difference among numbers of family size with $t=27.396$.

Size of land holding (LNDHLD): Land is the single and most important production resources base for any economic activity especially in rural and agricultural sector. In this study, the average land holding of sample respondents were found to be 0.675 hectare with standard deviation of 0.3295 hectare.

Therefore, result showed that, there were mean difference among the sample respondents with regarding of land holding with $t= 20.491$.

Livestock holding (NULPS): Livestock holding is an important indicator of wealth status for the beef cattle producers and it is an important source of cash, manure, draft power and beef cattle. The average livestock holding in TLU of the beef cattle producers' were 6. There were a mean difference among sample house hold of livestock holding with $t=23.406$.

Number of beef cattle (TNBOWN): Numbers of beef cattle holding is an important indicator of wealth status for beef cattle producers and it is an important source of meat. Average beef cattle'

holding of the sample households were 3. There were a mean difference among sample house hold of number of beef cattle owned with $t=27.067$.

Type of beef cattle used (BT): Type of beef cattle's was used for fattening by the farmers in the study areas were mainly local beef cattle and exotic beef cattle.

Source: own survey 2015

Figure4. 9: Types of beef cattle

About 98% of the respondent used of local beef cattle breed. While, 2% of sample respondents were used exotic breed. So, there were a different among the sample house hold holding the types of beef cattle with χ^2 -value =103.571 in the study area. So, it showed most beef cattle producers were used local beef cattle breeds but some beef cattle producers were used exotic beef cattle that are culled from their dairy farm.

Supplementary feed (FS): About 84 % of the respondents were providing supplementary feed to their beef cattle and those supplementary feed includes various content of feed. The provision of various types of supplementary feed gives energy for fattening of beef cattle. So, there was a different among the sample house hold providing of supplementary feed to their beef cattle (χ^2 -value =5.432).

Table4.11.Types of supplementary feed

Types of supplementary feed	Frequency	Percent
wheat bran	69	69
Sesame cake	15	15
Mixed of residual of <i>tela</i> , maize straw, hay and straw	42	42
Total	126	126

Source: own survey 2015

From the total of respondents about 42% of beef cattle producers were providing supplementary mixing local brewery by products with straw and hay straw and about 69 % of beef cattle producers provided wheat bran and 15 % of beef cattle producers provided sesame cake to their beef cattle.

Access to credit service (CRDTACS): Access to credit service is the source of finance for the income households to purchased beef cattle and inputs for beef cattle production. The credit service in the study area is given in cash form especially credit services delivered for beef cattle production. From the total about 94% of the sample respondents were got credit services for purpose of purchasing beef cattle and its inputs like drugs, feed, feed trough and purchasing others commodities. However, it is not enough available to the farmers. The microfinance institutions operating in the area, as farmers explained to us, do not have a full program to give credit for such. There were a different among sample house hold access to credit service with χ^2 -value =18.614. This implies that, farmers having an access to use credit service had a capacity to purchase beef cattle. Probably, it is also enhanced to purchase different beef cattle inputs than otherwise.

Extension service (EXTSRV): From the total sample households about 55 % of beef cattle producer's households were access to extension agents while about 45% of sample respondents were not access to extension agents. So, there were a different among sample house hold access to extension service and contact with extension service at χ^2 -value =20.159.

Market information (MRKTINF): About 71 % of the respondents had market information through personal observation, asking others beef cattle traders. While about 29% of sample respondents were not access to market information. So, there were a different among sample house hold access to market information with χ^2 -value =12.265.

Distance to nearest market(DSTNMKT): About 5 % of beef cattle producers sold their beef cattle to their nearest market place with an average distance of 15 Km. So, there were a mean different among sample respondents distance to nearest market with $t=3.599$.

Distance to main road (DSTMRTKT): Near to main road important for variable to the producers to get attractive market price through reduction of transportation cost. In this study, the sample house hold on average travelled about 10 km from their residential area to the main road. So, there were a mean difference distance to main road among sample house hold of beef cattle producers with $t=11.280$. Farmers nearby to the main roads centers have an opportunity to get

information on market price to consider cost of transportation and related problems of beef cattle supply to market. Additionally, those farmers has the probability to got market linkage with input supply office and feed ,medicine and other necessary for beef cattle sales to the markets.

4.3.2. Econometric Model Analysis

Before proceeding to see the relation of variables by using the OLS econometric model, it is important to look the problem of multi-collinearity or linear association among the hypothesized variables. Where the explanatory variables are highly correlated is referred to as Multi-co linearity. There are two measures that are often suggested to test the existence of multi-co linearity. These are: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for association between the continuous explanatory variables and Contingency Coefficients (CC) for categorical explanatory variables. The technique of variance inflation factor was working to detect the problem of multi-co linearity between the continuous variables. The highest the value of VIF the more could be collinear the variable and if the VIF of an explanatory variable greater than 10, there is a multi-co linearity problem. Thus, there were no as such serious of multi collinearity problem among continuous explanatory variables.

Likewise, contingency coefficients were computed to check the existence of multi-co linearity problem among the discrete categorical explanatory variables. The decision rule for contingency coefficients states that values less than 0.75 mean there is no problem of multi-co linearity. When the contingency coefficient approaches 1, it indicates that there is no a problem of multi-co linearity between the discrete variables. Based on the results of these tests, variables that have high degree of correlation were eliminated from further analysis. It was concluded that there was no multi-collinearity and association problems between a set of continuous and discrete variables, as the respective coefficients were very low. Linearity, het-eroscedasticity and Homoscedasticity of the model were checked in the appendix table 14 and 15. Finally the fourteen potential continuous and categorical variables were entered into the linear regression analysis.

4.3.2.1. Econometric Model Out put

The linear regression model presented to estimate the factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market in the study area.

Table4.12.Results of econometric model

Variable	Coef	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]
SEHH	.3262185	.7216694	0.45	0.652	-1.109153 1.76159
AGHH	-.0483234	.0299072	-1.62	0.110	-.1078075 .0111607
FAMSIZ	-.0488431	.1056295	-0.46	0.645	-.258936 .1612499
EDUCHHD	.0377779	.1108619	0.34	0.734	-.1827221 .2582778
LNDHLD	-.0905144	.1741941	-0.52	0.605	-.4369794 .2559507
NULPS	.0692413	.0796089	0.87	0.387	-.0890976 .2275803
BT	-1.034522	.5358914	-1.93	0.057*	-2.100389 .0313441
TNBROWN	.9721216	.2076875	4.68	0.000***	.5590395 1.385204
FS	.308488	.5887	0.52	0.602	-.8624127 1.479389
CRDTACS	2.381559	.8101681	2.94	0.004***	3.992951 .7701672
EXTSRV	.4225395	.4025784	1.05	0.297	-.3781727 1.223252
MRKTINF	.8386899	.4597668	1.82	0.072*	-.0757678 1.753148
DSTNBEFCMRT	-.0080197	.0070847	-1.13	0.261	-.0060715 .0221109
DSTMREFCMKT	-.0282731	.0068958	-4.10	0.000***	-.0145576 .0419886
_cons	4.089417	1.688751	2.42	0.018	.7305597 7.448274

Source: own survey 2015

Note: *** significant at 1%, ** at 5% and * at 10% level of significance

R Square= 0.498 Adjusted R Square=0.413 F =5.87 Sig F Change=0.000

From the total of fourteen variables five of them had influencing on quantity supply of beef cattle to the market. Those variables are distance to the main road, access to credit service, access to market information, breed type and numbers of beef cattle owned at 1% and 10% significant

level of significance respectively. On the contrary, the remaining eight non-significant explanatory variables were not the correct predictors of quantity supply of beef cattle to the market.

Number of beef cattle (TNBOWN): As expected this variable influences the quantity of beef cattle supply to market positively and statistically significant at ($p < 0.001$). This indicates that farmers with more number of beef cattle can have a better marketable surplus and could be supply more quantity. The positive coefficient indicated that an increase in quantity of beef cattle fattened increase volume of marketable supply of beef cattle by the farmers. It indicates that households who fattened more quantity of beef cattle have also supplied more to the market. The result also showed that increase in the quantity beef cattle owned has caused 0.97 number increment in the volume of marketable beef cattle being other variable held constant. This study agrees with the finding of Awol, (2010) and Holloway *et al.*, (2000).

Type of beef cattle used (BT): Fattened beef cattle to sell are influenced negatively by the types of beef cattle used for fattening and statistically significant at ($p < 0.1$). This can be explained as farmers possessing exotic breed supply have less volume than those who have local one. This is due to that even if the exotic breed is more productive in terms of meat yield. But due to feed requirements and disease vulnerability farmers could prefer the local breed type. The coefficient also indicated that as a beef cattle producers gets one more unit of exotic breed results to 1.04 number decrements in the quantity of beef cattle supplied to the market being other variables held constant.

Access to credit service (CRDTACS): Access to credit service is the source of finance for the households to Purchas beef cattle and inputs for its production. Access to credit could enhance the financial capacity of the farmers to purchase the necessary inputs for the marketing of beef cattle. Therefore, it hypothesized that credit use for beef cattle keeping and marketing have positive influence on quantity of beef cattle supplied to market.

Therefore, the analysis result revealed that, access to credit service shows statistically significant at ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, the coefficient shows that beef cattle producers those who received credit supply 2.4 number more beef cattle than those who did not receive credit. This implies that, farmers having an access to use credit service had capacity sale beef cattle. This study confirms the findings of Awol, (2010), Simeon *et al.*, (2011).

Market information (MRKTINF): As expected before, market information influences quantity supply of beef cattle to the market positively and significantly at ($p < 0.1$). This might be due to the fact that farmers having access to market information would be more likely to supply more quantity of beef cattle to the market as they are more likely to recover their marketing costs. Thus, we expect farmers getting market information supply more beef cattle to the market. Furthermore, the coefficient shows that beef cattle producers those who received beef cattle market information supply 0.84 more beef cattle than those who did not receive market information. This study confirms the findings of (Holloway *et al.*, 2000).

Distance of main road from residential area (DSTMR): nearest to main road is important for the producers to get attractive market price through reduction of transportation cost. In this study, the sample house hold on average travelled about 10 km from their residential area to the main road. So, distance of main roads from residential area had statistically significant at ($p < 0.001$) and negatively affects quantity supply of beef cattle to market. Because when distance of road from residential areas increases quantity supply of beef cattle to market could be negatively affects. This study confirmed the findings of (Lapar *et al.*, 2002).

4.4 .Challenges and opportunity of beef cattle value chain.

4.4.1. Challenges of beef cattle value chain

Table4.13.challenges of beef cattle value chain

No	Types of constraints	Index	Ranking
1.	Land	0.3015	1
2.	Credit problem	0.12953	2
3.	Capital	0.118	3
4.	Reliable markets found very far	0.115656	4
5.	Water constraints	0.105	5
6.	Lack of qualified market agent	0.104	6
7.	Lack of transportation	0.1	7
8.	Lack of experience on market	0.099671	8
9.	Shortage of beef cattle forage	0.09717	9
10.	seasonality of beef cattle production	0.0939	8
11.	Frequency change in demand and supply	0.0851	9
12.	Limited market buyers Disease	0.07568	10
13.	Breed type	0.075	11
14.	Market problem	0.07288	11
15.	Disease	0.0600375	12

From the Table 4.13 according to the beef cattle producers' small land holding is among the most distressing constraints in the beef cattle value chain. In addition to this the total respondent pointed out that shortage of land is the most important constraint in the area. They also added that shortage of credit access is most common factor among others in the study area. Access to credit service is constrained and as the respondent said problems were faced during giving credit such problems are not giving on time that means delaying during giving of credits and created disagreement among creditor's agents and some others problems are inaccessibility of credit agents, high interest rate, lack of enough availability and debt collection problem. Absence of capital and reliable markets found very far are also mentioned economically important challenges in beef cattle value chain.

According to beef cattle producers, there was no enough land allocated for beef cattle production but beef cattle producers were only produced in the land which was given for crop production activities.

Lack of qualified market agent also important marketing constrained in beef cattle value chain and marketing activities. Because, as the producers said information on training related to beef cattle value chain were not enough from the qualified market agent. But some respondents have got training related to beef cattle production by the extension service. Generally, according to the result presented in Table 4.13, the most frequently mentioned constraints were identified by sample producers like land, capital, credit service and lack of qualified market agent is most frequently mentioned constraint in beef cattle value chain in the study area. This result is in line with (Hailemariam *et al.*, 2009). These constraints created systematic inefficiencies at different stages of the marketing functions across the beef cattle value chain.

4.4.2. Opportunity of beef cattle value chain

Table4. 14: Opportunity of beef cattle value chain

No	Opportunity of beef cattle value chain	Frequency	Percent
1	Comfortable environmental condition for beef cattle fattening	89	89
2	There is good peace and security for purchasing and selling of matured cow	70	70
3	Important for improving living standards	68	68
4	Support by extension workers	42	42
5	Nearest to market	35	35

According to the Table 4.14 beef cattle value chain activities were avail ample opportunities for improving living standards in rural areas. Freely purchasing and selling matured cow, comfortable environmental condition for beef cattle production activities support by extension workers, cow fattening practice and existing of peace and security in the area were good opportunity for beef cattle value chain. The increasing price of beef cattle during ceremony such as: during New Year and Christmas provides real sustainable business opportunity for the beef cattle value chain activities in the study area

CHAPTER FIVE

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSION

Beef cattle production is the most important economic activity in households. It serves as a starter capital stock, source of easily disposable cash income and it is available opportunity for increase beef cattle value chain activities. Though, there were potential conditions for beef cattle production in the study area, the actors were constrained by different problems. Some of the identified constraints were land, credit service, capital, reliable markets found very far, water constraints and lack of qualified market agent.

As beef cattle transported from producers to consumers, marketing actors such as input suppliers, producers, collectors, traders, butchers, hotels and restaurants, Aberegele exporters and final consumers were the most marketing actors in Tahtay Koraro Woreda and with different roles were involved in purchasing and selling activities. The marketing costs and margins computation result of this study indicates that most producers were preferred to sell their beef cattle to Channel -IV: producers – consumers, Channel VI: producers –local collectors –Aberegele and Channel -III: producers –local collectors –large traders – Aberegele (exports).

From the model result factors affecting quantity supply of beef cattle to the market were: numbers of beef cattle owned, access to credit service and market information influences beef cattle supply to the market positively. Nevertheless, breed type and distance to main road were found influence the quantity of beef cattle supply to market negatively.

5.2. RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of this study, recommendations were described as follows:

- Governments and other development agent should focused to overcome constraints that make weak relationship among actors
- Producers should connect to channels based on highest percentage of producer's share of final price and minimum marketing costs
- So, input suppliers and extensions service should support to farmers for producing high quantity of beef cattle.
- Strengthening social organizations to empower the community to solve their own infrastructural problem through mobilizing locally available resource especially on constructing social infrastructure like road to transport beef cattle to the nearby market center is needed.
- Credit service should deliver on need-based to achieve the intended goals of the purchase beef cattle, inputs materials that are necessary for beef cattle production.
- Governments should informed farmers through mass media and radio. Thus farmers with higher access to market information could be more likely to participate in supply of beef cattle to market.

6. REFERENCES

- ACDI/VOCA, 2008. Djibouti Study Tour – Trip Report, Pastoralist Livelihoods Initiative – Livestock Marketing Program, August 26-28, 2008, 12 pp.
- Addisu, A., Solomon, M., Getachew, L., Solomon ,A., and Fantahun, D.2012. Beef and Feed Value Chain Study In Adama District. EIAR, Debre Zeit Agricultural Research Center, Ethiopia. Value Chain consultant, ILRI.PP 15-24
- AGP-Livestock Market Development Project, 2013. Agricultural Growth Project - Livestock Market Development, Value Chain Analysis for Ethiopia: Meat and Live Animals ,Hides, Skins and Leather and dairy .Expanding Livestock Markets for the Small-holder Producers. PP 12-48.
- Alemayehu, M. ,Wondatir, Z. ,Gojjam, Y., and W/Gebriel, K. 2003. Evaluation of Friesian x boran crossbred and Ethiopian Highland Zebu oxen with a reciprocal work effect on carcass characteristics. Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Holetta Agricultural Research Center, P.O. Box 2003, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, E-mail: zewbt2006@yahoo.com
- Alemayehu, K. 2011. Value chain assessment of beef cattle production and marketing in Ethiopia: Challenges and opportunities of linking smallholder farmers to the markets. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*.Volume 23, Article #255.Retrieved July 20, 2014, from <http://www.lrrd.org/lrrd23/12/alem23255.htm>
- Ayele, S.,Workalemahu, A., Jabar ,M. A., and Belachew, H .2003. Livestock Marketing in Ethiopia. A Review of Structure, Performance and Development Initiatives. Socio-economic and Policy Research Working Paper 52. International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), Nairobi, Kenya. 35p.
- Awol, Z.2010 .Analysis Of Poultry Market Chain: The Case of Dale And Alaba ‘Special’ Woredas of SNNPR, Ethiopia. Haramaya University.
- Bailey, D., Barrett, C .B., Little, P. D., and Chabari ,F. 1999 .Livestock markets and risk management among East African pastoralists: a review and research agenda”. GL-CRSP Pastoral Risk Management Project Technical Report No. 03/99. Utah State University.
- Belachew, H., and Jemberu, E. 2003. Challenges and opportunities of livestock marketing in Ethiopia. In: Jobre Y and Gebru G (eds), Challenges and opportunities of livestock

- marketing in Ethiopia. Proceedings of the 10th annual conference of the Ethiopian Society of Animal Production (ESAP) held in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 21–23 August 2002. ESAP, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. PP. 1–13.
- Berhanu, G., Hoekstra, D., and Samson, J. 2007. *Heading towards commercialization? The case of live animal marketing in Ethiopia*. Improving Productivity and Market Success (IPMS) of Ethiopian Farmers Project Working Paper 5. ILRI (International Livestock Research Institute), Nairobi, Kenya. 73 pp.
- BoANR, 2015. Burea of agricultural and natural resources .livestock statically description.
- BoANR, 2013. Burea of agricultural and natural resources .livestock statically description
- Board Tigray Region. 2004, Regional Annual Report. Mekelle, Tigray.
- Central Statistical Agency. 2012. Agricultural Sample Survey .2012. Volume II report on livestock and livestock characteristics. Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. (Private peasant holdings) Addis Ababa April 2013.
- Cetral mixed crop livelihood zone.2007. Livelihood profile tigray region,ethiopia.
- Gujarati, Damodar.2004: Basic Econometrics,Fourth Edition.The Mcgaw-Hill Campanies
- Daniel ,T .2008 .Beef Cattle Production System and Opportunities for Market Orientation in Borena Zone, Southern Ethiopia. A Thesis Submitted to the Departmentof Animal Science, School of Graduate Studies. Haramaya University, Ethiopia.
- Dolan, K, C. and J. Humphrey (2000), “Value chains and upgrading: The impact of UK retailers on the fresh fruit and vegetables industry in Africa”, *Journal of Development Studies*, Vol. 37, No. 2, pp. 147-176.
- Elias, M., Berhanu ,G., Hoekstra ,D., and Jabbar, M .2007. Analysis of the Ethio-Sudan cross-border cattle trade: The case of Amhara Regional State. IPMS (Improving Productivity and Market Success) of Ethiopian Farmers Project Working Paper 4. ILRI (International Livestock Research Institute), Nairobi, Kenya. 41 pp.
- FAO. 2012. Designing and implementing livestock value chain studies – A practical aid for Highly Pathogenic and Emerging Disease (HPED) control. FAO Animal Production and Health Guidelines No. 10. Rome. 27 pp.

- Gebregziabher, Gebreyohannes., and Gebrehiwot, Hailemariam .2011. Challenges, Opportunities and Available Good Practices related to Zero Grazing in Tigray and Hararghe, Ethiopia .DCG Report No. 66.
- GebreMariam, S., Amare, S., Baker, D., Solomon, A. and Davies, R. 2013.Study of the Ethiopian live cattle and beef value chain.ILRI Discussion Paper 23. Nairobi: International Livestock Research Institute.
- Gujirati, D. N., 2004. Basic Econometrics. McGraw - Hill Co. New York.
- Giuliani, E., Pietrobelli ,C., and Rabellotti ,R. 2005. Upgrading in global value chains: Lessons from Latin American clusters, *World Development* 33(4), pp. 549-573.
- Hailemariam, Gebreyohannes., and Gebrehiwot, Gebregziabher.2011. Challenges, Opportunities and Available Good Practices related to Zero Grazing in Tigray and Hararghe, Ethiopia .DCG Report No. 66.
- Hailemariam, Teklewold., Getachew, Legese., and Dawit Alemu.2009. Market Structure and Function for Live Animal and Meat Exports in Some Selected Areas of Ethiopia: Website: <http://www.eiar.gov.et>
- Holloway, G. J.,Nicholson, C., Delgado, C., Ehui, S. and Staal, S. 2000. Agroindustrialization Through Institutional Innovation: Transaction Costs, Cooperatives and Milk-Market Development in the East African Highlands.
- James. E., Bartlett, II,JoeW.Kotrlik Chadwick C.Higgins .2001. Organizational Research: Determining Appropriate Sample Size in Survey Research: *Information Technology, Learning, and Performance Journal*, Vol. 19, No. 1
- Kaplinsky , M .2001. A Handbook for Value Chain Research. Working Paper Prepared for the IDRC, Brighton, UK, Institute for Development Studies.
- Kaplinsky , M .2000. A Handbook for Value Chain Research. Working Paper Prepared for the IDRC, Bellagio, UK, Institute for Development Studies.PP 6
- Kothari, C.R., 1990. *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. Second Edition. Washwa Prakashan, New Delhi, India.
- KIT and IIRR. 2006. Trading up, Building cooperation between farmers and traders in Africa. Royal Tropical Institute, Amsterdam; and International Institute of Rural Reconstruction, Nairobi.

- Lapar, Ma. L., Holloway, G., and Ehui, S. 2002. Policy Options for Promoting Smallholder Market Participation: A Case Study from the Philippines. Socio-Economics and Policy Research Working Paper 47. International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), Nairobi, Kenya, 21 pp.
- Legese , G., and Teklewold , Hailemariam., and Alemu, Dawit. and Negassa, Afar. 2008. Live animal and meat export value chains for selected areas in Ethiopia: Constraints and opportunities for enhancing meat exports: Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, TAES: SPS {LMM, International Livestock Research Institute Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- LMA , 2004. Meat Exports Market Study, MoARD,b Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. In: New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) – Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP), 2005. Ethiopia: Investment Project Profile “Live Animal and Meat Export” Preliminary Options Outline.
- Nagasaki, A., and Jabber, M. 2008. Livestock ownership, commercial off-take rates and their determinants in Ethiopia. ILRI Research Report No. 9. Nairobi: ILRI (International Livestock Research Institute).
- NEPAD–CAADP (New Partnership for Africa's Development – Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme) 2005 Ethiopia: Investment Project Profile “Live Animal and Meat Export” – Preliminary Options Outline. 3pp.
- Pietrobelli ,F .2008. Power relationships along the value chain: multinational firms, global buyers and performance of local suppliers, Cambridge Journal of Economics, 32(6), pp. 947-962.
- Rangaswamy, R. 2007. Agricultural Statistics. New Age International Publisher, New Delhi. Pp. 211-214.
- Simeon, Ehui. Samuel, Benin and Zelekawork, Paulos, 2011. Policy options for improving market participation and sales of smallholder Livestock producers: A case study of Ethiopia., Paper submitted to the 2nd EAF International Conference on Contemporary Development issues in Ethiopia Addis Ababa International Livestock Research Institute.
- Sintayehu, GebreMariam., Samuel ,Amare., Derek ,Baker., and Ayele, Solomon .2010. Diagnostic study of live cattle and beef production and marketing: Constraints and opportunities for enhancing the system. Consultant to International Food Policy Research Institute (July 2010).PP 15-30

- Sintayehu, GebreMariam., Samuel ,Amare., Derek ,Baker., and Ayele, Solomon .2013.Study of the Ethiopian live cattle and beef value chain.ILRI Discussion Paper 23. Nairobi: International Livestock Research Institute. PP 2-35
- SPS-LMM .2010.Trade Bulletin Issue I. Focus on Ethiopia's meat and Live Animal Export.
- SPS-LMM .2011.Trade Bulletin Issue 4. Focus on Ethiopia's meat and Live Animal Export.PP14
- Stock, H., Bezabih Emana, Birhanu Adnew, Borowiecki, A. and Shimeles W/Hawariate, 1991. Farming systems and farm management practices of small holders in the Hararghe Highlands: Farming systems and resources economics in the tropics. Wissenschaftsverlagvauk, Kiel, Germany. 11: 41-48.
- Workneh ,A. 2006. Getting the Incentives Right: Concerns Associated with Expansion of Cattle Export Markets in Ethiopia. Ethiopian Journal of Animal Production 6(2), 99-103.
- Williams, T. 2006. Improving livestock marketing and intraregional trade in West Africa: Determining appropriate economic incentives and policy framework. ILRI (International Livestock Research Institute), Nairobi, Kenya. 122 pp.
- Yacob , A. 2010. Livestock Exports from Pastoralist Areas: An Analysis of Benefits by Wealth Group and Policy Implications. IGAD LPI Working Paper No. 01-10. 41- 52 pp.
- Yishak, B .2013. Livestock and Irrigation Value-Chain for Ethiopian Smallholders (LIVES) Gamo Gofa Zone Diagnosis and Planning Document, SNNP.23 pp.

7. APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Interview schedule

Questionnaire for data collection

General information

- Questionnaire number/ID: _____
- Region: _____
- Zone: _____
- Woreda/District: _____
- Keble/Tibia: _____
- Date of Interview: _____
- Agro-ecology: _____

A. Demographic characteristics of households

1. Gender of the household: 1. Male 0. Female
2. Age of the household head: _____ years
3. Marital status of the household head: 1.Married 2.not married 3.Divorced 4.Widow 5. Separated
4. Family size including adults and children: Male:___ Female:___ Total___
5. Education level of the household head

s/n	Education level of the household head	Urban	Rural	Occupation
1.	Illiterate (can not read and write)			
2.	Read and write			
3.	Grade 1-4			
4.	Grade 5-8			
5.	Grade 9-10			
6.	Grade 11-12			
7.	College and university			

B. Size of land holding

1. Do you have your own land? 1. Yes 0. No 2. If your answer to Q 4 is yes, Size of land holding (ha) _____

C. livestock production

1. Do you have livestock? 1. Yes 0. No

2. If your answer to Q 1 is yes how many livestock do you have (in 2015)?

Type of livestock	No .of animals owned
<u>Cattle</u>	
Lactating cows	
Dry cows	
Calves	
Heifer	
Bull	
Oxen	
Shoats	
Sheep	
Goat	
Equines	
Donkey	
Horse	
Mule	
Exotic poultry	
Local poultry	

C.1. Beef production Issues

1. What type of beef cattle Breed do you own?

No.	Breed of beef cattle	No .of beef cattle owned	Reason for choosing
1	Local breed		
2	Exotic breed		
3	Cross breed		

2. What is your source of beef cattle?

No	Sources	Yes	No
1	Market		
2	producing		

3. If the answer for Q3 is from market, from where do you buy? List all the options in your areas _____

4. Currently do you produce beef cattle? 1. Yes 0. No

5. If the answer for Q 5 is yes, for what purpose do you produce beef cattle? (Circle one or more)

1. For home consumption 0. For income generation

6. What are supplementary feed types given to beef cattle?

No	Supplementary feed type
1	Wheat bran
2	Sesame cack
3	Urea molasses block
4	Urea treatment
5	Others _____
6	Total

1. Beef cattle production trend

Beef cattle production	Trend of beef productivity		
	Increasing	Decreasing	Steady
Local breed			
Cross/ breed			
Exotic breed			

D. Credit and Extension Service issues

1. Do you have access to credit? 1. Yes 0. No
2. If your answer for Q 1 is yes, for what purpose do you take the credit?
 1. For beef cattle production 2. To purchase beef cattle 3. To purchase food grains
 4. To purchase for cloth 5. Others (specify)_____
3. If your answer to Q 1 is yes, who is the service provider? 1. Micro finance institution 2. NGO 3. Friends 4. Relatives 5. Money lenders 6. Peasant association 7. Others (specify)_____
4. What are the major problems you face to get input on credit?
 1. Inaccessibility of credit agents 1. Yes _____ 0. No _____
 2. Debit collection problem 1. Yes _____ 0. No _____
 3. High interest rate 1. Yes _____ 0. No _____
 4. Unavailability of other credit organization as option 1. Yes _____ 0. No _____
 5. Availability but not enough 1. Yes _____ 0. No _____
 6. Others, specify: _____
5. Do you provide extension workers service for beef cattle production and marketing? 1. Yes 0.no
6. If your answer to Q 5 is yes how often do extension service providers meet you?
 1. Regularly 2. Some times
7. If your answer to Q 5 is yes how often did you got technical advice on beef cattle production and/or marketing by the extension service providers? 1. Regularly 2. Some times 3. Not at all/never

E. market information

- 1. Do you get access of market information? 1. Yes 2.no
 - 2. If your answer is yes to Q 1 what is the major source of updated information for farm households on beef cattle market?
 - 1. Personal observation 2. Other beef cattle traders 3.Telephone 4.Rdio
 - 3. Did you know the market prices before you sold your beef cattle? 1=Yes 0=No
 - 4. How do you get market price information of beef cattle?
-

F. beef cattle marketing issues

- 1. What opportunities exist to participate in beef cattle market?1. Access to near market, 2.Full access to information 3. Having large number of beef cattle 4. Financial income motive 5. Others (specify)_____
- 2. To whom do you sell your beef cattle?
 - 1. Collectors 2. Traders 3.Hotels /restaurants 4.Processors 5. Broker 6.consumers
 - 7. Super markets
- 3. Where is the place of market to sell the beef cattle? 1. Farm gate 2.local market 3.town 4. Local nearby market 5.distance markets in bigger towns
- 4. If transport how many kms do you travel on average to markets to sell your beef cattle?
 - 1. How far is the market place from your residential to nearby local markets (Primary markets) _____ Kms
 - 2. To urban markets (Secondary markets) _____ Kms
- 5. How far is the main road from your residential area? _____Kms
- 6. Who are your major customers? List them by order (sell your beef cattle 1st,2nd,etc...)
 - ____local consumers? ____NGOs ____Cooperatives
 - ____Market ____Government institutions
 - ____traders
 - ____Retailers ____collectors ____Other (specify) _____

7. What is the annual income from sale of beef cattle?

No	Types of beef cattle	Quantity	Unit price (Birr)	Total price (Birr)
1	Matured male beef cattle			
2	Matured female cattle			
3	Young beef cattle			
4	Exotic beef cattle			

8. What were the problems created by traders?

1. Cheating on quality of beef cattle
2. Wrong price (market) information
3. Others (specify) _____

9. Did you face difficulty in finding buyers when you wanted to sell beef cattle?

1= yes 0= No

10. If your answer to Q 23 is yes it is due to: _

1. Inaccessibility of market
2. Fasting days
3. Lack of information
4. Low price offered
5. Others (specify) _____

11. What do you do if you didn't get the expected price for your beef cattle?

1. Took back home
2. Sold at lower price

12. Took to another market on the same day 4. Sold on other market day 5. Others (specify) _____

H. Interaction among value chain actors

1. How do you see your relationship with your beef cattle traders and consumers?

1. Strong
2. weak
3. doesn't exist

2. How do you see your relationship with government?

1. Strong
2. weak
3. doesn't exist

3. Do you collect and give information from your sellers and buyers on the amount and quality required? 1. Always 2. Some times 3. Not at all

4. What factors constrained the linkage between beef cattle value chain actors?

1. Policy 2.Organizational 3.Infrastructure 4.KSA (Knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation 5.others (specify)_____

J.Constraints /challenges and opportunities

1. What are the major constraints of beef cattle in the area? (Rank them)

No	Constraints	1=Yes; 0=No	Rank	What measures will be taken?
1	Land			
2	Credit problem			
3	Capital			
4	Lack of qualified market agent			
5	Shortage of beef cattle forage			
6	Lack of experience on market			
7	Market problem			
8	Frequency change in demand and supply			
9	Breed type			
10	Frequency change in demand and supply			
11	Breed type			
12	Disease			
13	Brokers hinder fair selling			
14	Water constraints			
15	Reliable markets found very far			
16	Tax problem			
17	Lack of transportation			

N.B 1=most sever 2=second sever, etc

2. What are the major beef cattle Marketing opportunity in your area?

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

3. Comments, Suggestions and Recommendations

3.1. What do you recommend to improve beef cattle value chain in the future?

1. _____

2. _____

2. Traders' questionnaire

Remark: The personal profile obtained from respondents with regard to the theme will be kept confidential and will not have any consequence on the respondent in any ways. Please give correct answers to the following questions.

Instructions to Enumerators

- Make brief introduction before starting any question, introduce yourself to the farmers, greet them in local ways and make clear the objective of the study.
- Please fill the interview schedule according to the farmers reply (do not put your own feeling).
- Please ask each question clearly and patiently until the farmer gets your points.
- Please do not use technical terms and do not forget local units.
- Put the answer on the space provided

Objectives of the study

- To assess the linkage of actors b/n different participants
- To assess profit margin analysis b/n actors and mapp out
- To identify factors affecting supply of beef cattle to the market
- To assess the challenges and opportunities of beef cattle value chain

Checklist for other participants/actors in the value chain

I .Local beef cattle collectors

Questionnaire number/ID: _____

Region: _____

Zone: _____

Wereda/District: _____

Kebele/Tabia: _____

Date of Interview: _____

I. Purchase practice

1. From where did you purchase beef cattle?

1. From village market, name of village market (specify) _____

2. From town market, name of town market (specify) _____

3. Direct from Producers

2. How do you attract suppliers?

1. Giving better price 2.by visiting them 3.other _____

3. Who purchase beef cattle for you?

1. Myself 2.broker 3.commission agent

4. Family members 5.friends 6. others _____

4. To whom do you sell your beef cattle?

1. To consumer 2. To Processors 3. Traders

5. Estimated cost for beef cattle market

No	Different costs	Birr/one
1	Purchasing price of mature male of beef cattle from producers	
2	Purchasing price of female beef cattle from producers	
3	Purchasing price of young beef cattle from producers	
4	Exotic beef cattle	
5	Mixed breed	
6	Labor cost	
7	Transportation cost	
8	Distribution Cost	
9	Personal transport	
Total		

6. Is obtaining sufficient volume is a problem? 1=yes, 0=No

7. From which market(s) do you prefer to buy most of the time? From_____ market.

8. Why do you prefer this market?

1. Better quality 3.high supply
2. Shortest distance 4.low price 5.others _____

9. Please tell me the selling price of the beef cattle?

Selling price of matured male beef cattle from producers? _____Birr/head

Selling price of matured female beef cattle from producers?_____Birr/head

Selling price of young beef cattle from producers? _____Birr/head

Selling price of exotic beef cattle from producers?_____Birr/head

Selling price of mixed breed beef cattle from producers?_____Birr/head

Interaction among value chain actors

1. How do you see your relationship with your beef cattle traders and consumers?

1. Strong 2.weak 3.doesn't exist

2. How do you see your relationship with government?

1. Strong 2.weak 3.doesn't exist

3. Do you collect and give information from your sellers and buyers on the amount and quality required? 1. Always 2. Some times 3.Not at all

4. What factors constrain the linkage between beef cattle value chain actors?

1. Policy 2.organizational 3.infrastructure 4.KSA (Knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation 4.others (specify)_____

5. What do you recommend to improve beef cattle value chain in the future?

II. Traders

Questionnaire number/ID: _____

Region: _____

Zone: _____

Wereda/District: _____

Kebele/Tabia: _____

Date of Interview: _____

1. Where do you buy beef cattle?

1. Farm gets 2. local market 3. city/town market

2. To whom do you sell your beef cattle?

1. To consumer 2. To hotels 3. retailer 4. butchers

3. Estimated cost for beef market

No	Different costs	Birr/one	When purchased from d/t source
1	Purchasing price of matured male beef cattle		
2	Purchasing price of matured female beef cattle		
3	Purchasing price of young beef cattle		
3	Purchasing price of exotic breed beef cattle		
4	Purchasing price of mixed breed beef cattle		
4	Transportation cost		
5	Tax		
6	Shop Rent		
7	Distribution cost		
8	Personal transport		
9	Feed cost		
Total			

4. Is obtaining sufficient volume is a problem? 1= Yes, 0= No

5. From which market (s) do you prefer to buy most of the time? From _____ market.

6. Why do you prefer this market?

1. Better quality 3. High supply 2. Shortest distance 4. Low price 5. Others _____

7. Please tell me the selling price of the beef cattle?

1. Selling price of matured male beef cattle from producers? _____ Birr

2. Selling price of matured female beef cattle from producers? _____ Birr
3. Selling price of young beef cattle from producers? _____ Birr
4. Selling price of exotic beef cattle from producers? _____ Birr
5. Selling price of mixed beef cattle from producers? _____ Birr

Interaction among value chain actors

1. How do you see your relationship with your beef cattle traders and consumers?
 1. Strong 2.weak 3.doesn't exist
2. How do you see your relationship with government?
 1. Strong 2.weak 3.doesn't exist
3. Do you collect and give information from your sellers and buyers on the amount and quality required?
 1. Always 2. Some times 3. Not at all
4. What factors constrain the linkage between beef cattle value chain actors?
 1. Policy 2. organizational 3. infrastructure 4. KSA (Knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation 4. others (specify) _____
5. What do you recommend to improve beef cattle value chain in the future?

III. Hotels and restaurants

Questionnaire number/ID: _____

Region: _____

Zone: _____

Wereda/District: _____

Kebele/Tabia: _____

Date of Interview: _____

1. Where do you buy beef cattle?

1. Farm get 2.local market 3.city/town market 4. Producers 5. Collectors
6. Traders

2. How many regular suppliers do you have? 1. Producer _____ 2. Local traders _____

3. large traders _____ 4. Others (specify) _____

3. To whom do you sell your beef cattle?

4. Do you get the desired amount and type of beef cattle product continuously in the market?

1=yes, 0=No

5. Estimated cost for beef cattle market

No	Different costs	Birr/one
1	Purchasing price of matured male beef cattle	
2	Purchasing price of matured female beef cattle	
3	Purchasing price of young beef cattle	
4	Purchasing price of exotic beef cattle	
5	Transportation cost	
6	Tax	
7	Rent for house	
8	Cost of handling material	
9	Labor cost	
10	Feed cost	
11	Telephone cost	
12	Electricity	
13	Food oil	
14	Salt	
15	Chills	

Selling price

1. What type of processed beef cattle product did you prepared for sale?

1. Cooked beef meat (tibs) 2.raw meat 3.keywet

s/n	Types of beef cattle product	Price /matured male beef cattle	Price /matured female beef cattle	Price /matured beef cattle
1	Cooked beef meat (<i>tibs</i>)			
2	<i>raw meat</i>			
3	<i>Keywet</i>			
Total				

Interaction among beef cattle value chain actors:

1. How do you see your relationship with your beef cattle stakeholders?
1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist
2. How do you see your relationship with government?
1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist
3. Do you collect and give information from your sellers and buyers on the amount and quality of beef cattle required? 1. Always 2. Some times 3. Not at all
4. What factors constrain the linkages between beef cattle value chain actors?
1. Policy 2. Organizational 3. Infrastructure 4. KSA(knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation)
5. Others (specify)___
5. What do you recommend to improve beef cattle value chain in the future?

III .Butchers

Questionnaire number/ID: _____ Region: _____
Zone: _____ Wereda/District: _____
Kebele/Tabia: _____ Date of Interview: _____

1. Where do you buy beef cattle?
1. Farm get 2.local market 3.city/town market 4. Producers 5. Collectors
6. Traders
2. How many regular suppliers do you have? 1. Producer _____ 2. Assembler _____
3. Wholesalers _____ 4. Retailers _____ 5. Others (specify) _____
3. To whom do you sell your beef cattle?
1. To consumer 2. To hotel and restaurant
4. Do you get the desired amount and type of beef cattle product continuously in the market?
1=yes, 0=No

5. Estimated cost for beef cattle market

No	Different costs	Birr/one
1	Purchasing price of matured male beef cattle	
2	Purchasing price of matured female beef cattle	
3	Purchasing price of young beef cattle	
4	Purchasing price of exotic beef cattle	
5	Transportation cost	
6	Tax	
7	Rent for house	
8	Cost of handling material	
9	Labor cost	
10	Feed cost	
11	Telephone cost	
12	Electricity	
13	Food oil	
14	Salt	
15	Chills	
Total		

Selling price

1. What type of processed beef cattle product did you prepared for sale?

1. Cooked beef meat (*tibs*) 2.raw meat 3.keywet

s/n	Types of beef cattle product	Price /matured male beef cattle	Price /matured female beef cattle	Price /matured young beef cattle
1	Cooked beef meat (<i>tibs</i>)			
2	<i>raw meat</i>			
3	<i>Keywet</i>			
Total				

Interaction among beef cattle value chain actors:

1. How do you see your relationship with your beef cattle stakeholders?
 1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist
 2. How do you see your relationship with government?
 1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist
 3. Do you collect and give information from your sellers and buyers on the amount and quality of beef cattle required? 1. Always 2. Some times 3. Not at all
 4. What factors constrain the linkages between beef cattle value chain actors? 1. Policy 2. Organizational 3. Infrastructure 4. KSA(knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation 5. Others (specify)____
 5. What do you recommend to improve beef cattle value chain in the future?
-
-

IV. Consumers

Questionnaire number/ID: _____ Region: _____
Zone: _____
Wereda/District: _____ Kebele/Tabia: _____
Date of Interview: _____

1. How frequent do you consuming beef cattle ?
 1. Regularly (main activity) 2. Some times (occasionally)
2. Where do you buy beef cattle?
 1. from farm 2. from local market 3. from town market 4. Direct from Producers
 3. From Collectors 6. From Butchers 7. From Traders 8. from retailers
3. How many regular suppliers do you have? 1. Producer _____ 3. Assembler _____
 2. Wholesalers _____ 4. Retailers _____ 5. Others (specify) _____
4. Do you get the desired amount and type of beef cattle product continuously in the market?
1=yes, 0=No
5. From where do you buy your beef cattle?
 1. Producers 2. Collectors 3. traders 4. retailers 5. butchers

6. What is the price of beef cattle in the different market agents?

Agents	Price of beef cattle			
	Matured male beef cattle	Matured female beef cattle	Young beef cattle	Purchasing price of exotic beef cattle
Producers				
Traders				
Collectors				
Retailers				
Wholesalers				
Processors				

7. From whom do you prefer to purchase beef cattle? Why

1. Direct from producer 2. From collectors 3. From retailers 4. From wholesalers

Why? _____

8. At what time did you observe those beef cattle prices are cheap?

9. At what time did you observe those beef cattle prices are expensive?

10. What type of beef cattle do you prefer to purchase? Why

1. Local breed 2. Cross breed 3. Exotic breed

11. Are you satisfied by the beef cattle you are purchasing currently? 1= yes 0=No

12. If No why? _____

13. What problem do you influence your frequency of purchasing beef cattle?

Interaction among beef cattle value chain actors:

1. How do you see your relationship with your beef cattle agent?

1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist

2. How do you see your relationship with government?

1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist

3. Do you collect and give information from your sellers and buyers on the amount and quality of beef cattle required? 1. Always 2. Some times 3. Not at all

4. What factors constrain the linkages between beef cattle value chain actors?

5. Policy 2. Organizational 3. Infrastructure 4. KSA(knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation

4. Others (specify)____

6. What do you recommend to improve beef cattle value chain in the future?

V. Input Suppliers

Questionnaire number/ID: _____

Region: _____

Zone: _____

Wereda/District: _____

Kebele/Tabia: _____

Date of Interview: _____

1. Where is the source of inputs you supplying to the beef cattle producers?

1. Woreda agricultural office 2. Brought from traders 3. Made my small and micro enterprises 4. Others _____

2. How do you see the importance of your input in improving beef cattle production?

1. Very strong 2. Strong 3. Weak 4. Very weak

3. Are you known as input supplier in the area? 1=yes, 0 =No

4. If yes Q3, how is the quality of you beef cattle input?

1. Very good, 2. Good 3. Poor, 4 very poor

15. How is the price of your input for beef cattle production?

1. Very expensive 2. Expensive 3. Cheap 4. Very cheap

Interaction among beef cattle value chain actors:

1. How do you see your relationship with your beef cattle agent?

1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist

2. How do you see your relationship with government?

1. Strong 2. Weak 3. Doesn't exist

3. Do you collect and give information from your sellers and buyers on the amount and quality of beef cattle required? 1. Always 2. Some times 3. Not at all

4. What factors constrain the linkages between beef cattle value chain actors?

5. Policy 2. Organizational 3. Infrastructure 4. KSA(knowledge, skill, attitude and motivation

4. Others (specify)____

6. What do you recommend to improve beef cattle value chain in the future?

End of the interview

Thank you very much for responding to the questions.

Name of the Enumerator: _____ Date of Interview:_____

Appendix table 1: Estimation of beef cattle in producers

annual income from sale of beef cattle	N	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
matured male beef cattle	100	0	4	106	1.06	.422
Quantity	100	0	10	349	3.49	1.951
Unit price	100	0	8000	628166	6281.66	1116.702
Total price	100	0	70000	2203200	22032.00	14064.124
Matured female beef cattle	100	0	2	14	.14	.513
Quantity	100	0	5	16	.16	.647
Unit price	100	0	6500	43500	435.00	1496.891
Total price	100	0	32500	90000	900.00	3886.652
young beef cattle	100	0	3	72	.72	1.288
Quantity	100	0	5	54	.54	1.077
Unit price	100	0	8000	151000	1510.00	2731.208
Total prices	100	0	30000	336500	3365.00	6635.098
Exotic beef cattle	100	0	4	4	.04	.400
Quantity	100	0	1	1	.01	.100
Unit price	100	0	10000	10000	100.00	1000.000
Total price	100	0	10000	10000	100.00	1000.000

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 2: Estimated costs for beef cattle in producers

Other costs	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Feed cost beef	100	200	8320	249470	2494.70	1433.779
Labor cost beef	100	0	2000	6510	65.10	263.912
Medication cost	99	0	882	20687	208.96	111.621
Loading and unloading cost	100	0	450	824	8.24	51.127
Transporting cost	100	0	900	6765	67.65	136.788
Tax	100	0	100	331	3.31	13.762
Feed and water cost	100	60	560	22025	220.25	103.637

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 3: Estimated costs for beef cattle in local collectors

Estimated cost	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
price of mature male of beef cattle	5	32500	68000	279500	55900.00	15339.492
Quantity	5	.0	4.00	7.00	1.4000	1.67332
price of female beef cattle	5	0	22800	44300	8860.00	9599.375
Quantity	5	.00	8.00	11.00	2.2000	3.49285
price of young beef cattle	5	0	54400	74800	14960.00	23751.379
Telephone and electric	5	200	3000	4200	840.00	1211.610
Labor cost	5	0	3000	5000	1000.00	1414.214
Personal transport	5	150	1100	3150	630.00	405.586
Feed and medication cost	5	2890	3800	16170	3234.00	396.459

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 4: Selling price of beef cattle in local collectors

selling price of the beef cattle	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Quantity	5	5.00	11.00	44.00	8.8000	2.38747
Selling price of matured male beef cattle from producers	5	40000	82500	333500	66700.00	18185.159
Quantity	5	.00	4.00	7.00	1.4000	1.67332
Selling price mature beef cattle	5	0	30000	54700	10940.00	12582.448
Quantity	5	.00	8.00	11.00	2.2000	3.49285
Selling price of young cattle	5	0	68000	90500	18100.00	29547.420

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 5: Estimated costs for beef cattle marketing in traders

Estimated Cost For Beef Cattle Market	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
Quantity	5	5.00	11.00	44.00	8.8000
Purchasing price of beef cattle	5	32500	68000	279500	55900.00
Quantity	5	.00	4.00	7.00	1.4000
Purchasing price of female beef cattle	5	0	22800	44300	8860.00
Quantity	5	.00	8.00	11.00	2.2000
Purchasing price of young beef cattle	5	0	54400	74800	14960.00
Telephone and electric	5	200	3000	4200	840.00
Labor cost	5	0	3000	5000	1000.00
Personal transport	5	150	1100	3150	630.00
Feed and medication cost	5	2890	3800	16170	3234.00

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 6: Selling price of beef cattle in traders

Selling price of the beef cattle	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
Quantity	5	5.00	11.00	44.00	8.8000
Selling price of matured male beef cattle from producers	5	40000	82500	333500	66700.00
Quantity	5	.00	4.00	7.00	1.4000
Selling price of mature female beef cattle	5	0	30000	54700	10940.00
Quantity	5	.00	8.00	11.00	2.2000
Selling price of young cattle	5	0	68000	90500	18100.00

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 7: Estimated cost for beef cattle in butchers

Estimated cost for beef cattle market	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Purchasing price of matured male beef cattle	5	6	100	156	31.20	38.951
Unit price	5	6500.00	7833.00	35333.00	7066.60	652.248
Total price	5	26000	783300.00	1070300	214060	322097.6
Purchased price of mature female beef cattle	5	0	10	28	5.60	5.177
Unit price	5	.00	6500.00	19500.00	3900.0000	3560.19
Total price	5	.00	65000.00	174000.00	34800.0000	32904.40
Purchasing price of young beef cattle	5	0	7500	28000	5600.00	3150.397
Total price	5	0	150000	260000	52000.00	57410.800
Exotic beef cattle	5	0	4	7	1.40	1.949
Unit price	5	0	9000	17000	3400.00	4669.047
Total price	5	0	36000	60000	12000.00	16970.563

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 8: Estimated cost of materials in butchers

Transportation person	5	500	5000	11200	2240.00	1658.086
Tax	5	50	500	1120	224.00	165.809
Labor cost	5	2000	20000	44800	8960.00	6632.345
Electricity and water	5	500	5000	11200	2240.00	1658.086
Oil cost	5	1250	12500	28000	5600.00	4145.216
Onion	5	1500	15000	33600	6720.00	4974.259
Chills	5	3200	32000	71680	14336.00	10611.752
Teff	5	5000	50000	112000	22400.00	16580.862
Rent for house	5	3500	35000	78400	15680.00	11606.604
For abattoirs	5	1500.00	15000.00	33900.00	6780.0000	4958.40196

Sources: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 9: selling price of beef cattle in butchers

Selling price of the beef cattle	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Selling price of matured male beef cattle	5	6.00	100.00	156.00	31.2000	38.95125
Raw meat and cooking meat	5	9435.00	10710.00	49852.50	9970.5000	513.177
Total price	5	57375	994500	1551675	310335	387129.5
Selling price mature female beef cattle	5	.00	10.00	28.00	5.6000	5.17687
Raw meat and cooking meat	5	.00	10837.50	30727.50	6145.5000	5621.8
Total price	5	.00	99450.00	285600.00	57120.0000	52402.344
Selling price of young cattle	5	.00	20.00	36.00	7.2000	7.56307
Raw meat and cooking meat	5	.00	11092.50	41565.00	8313.0000	4665
Total price	5	.00	204000.0	371785.00	74357.0000	77001.8
Selling price exotic beef cattle	5	.00	4.00	7.00	1.4000	1.94936
Raw meat and cooking meat	5	.00	10200.00	20400.00	4080.0000	5586.77009
Total price	5	.00	40800.00	71400.00	14280.0000	19883.46

Source: own survey, 2015

Appendix table 10: Estimated price of beef cattle in hotels and restaurants

Estimated costs	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Quantity	5	100	100	500	100.00	.000
Unit price	5	6700.00	8000.00	37866.00	7573.2	520.8135
Total price	5	670000.00	800000.00	3786600.00	757320	52081.349
Transportation person	5	3000	6000	23000	4600.00	1140.175
Tax	5	200	500	2100	420.00	130.384
Labor cost	5	10000	30000	95000	19000.00	7416.198
Electricity and water	5	2000	6000	22000	4400.00	1516.575
Oil cost	5	1300	14000	52300	10460.00	5175.229
Onion	5	12000	15000	69000	13800.00	1303.840
Chills	5	20000	33000	146000	29200.00	5263.079
Teff	5	20000	50000	190000	38000.00	13038.405
Rent for house	5	32000	36000	172000	34400.00	1516.575
For abattoirs	5	14000.00	17000.00	77000.00	15400.000	1140.175
Quantity	5	100.00	100.00	500.00	100.0000	.00000
Raw meat	5	9945.00	12000.00	52945.00	10589.000	903.938
Total price	5	994500.00	1200000.	5294500.0	1058900.	90393.8604

Source: own survey, 2015

Appendix table 11: Estimated price of beef cattle in direct consumers

Estimated cost for beef cattle market	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Quantity	5	9.00	10.00	49.00	9.8000	.44721
Purchasing price of matured male beef cattle	5	75000.00	85000.00	405000.00	81000.0000	4183.30013
Purchased price of mature female beef cattle	3	2.00	3.00	7.00	2.3333	.57735
Purchasing price of young beef cattle	5	0	22500	48700	9740.00	9684.420
Purchasing price of exotic beef cattle	2	2.00	4.00	6.00	3.0000	1.41421
Matured female	5	0	22000	33000	6600.00	9838.699

Source: Own survey, 2015

Appendix table 12: Estimated price of beef cattle in Aberegele

Estimated cost for beef cattle market	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean
Quantity	1	31.00	31.00	31.00	31
Purchasing price of mature male of beef cattle	1	258850	258850	258850	258850
Quantity	1	48.00	48.00	48.00	48.0000
Purchasing price of young beef cattle	1	288000	288000	288000	288000
Labor cost	1	43200	43200	43200	43200
Transportation	1	5016	5016	5016	5016
Personal transport	1	1440	1440	1440	1440
Feed and medication cost	1	88875	88875	88875	88875

Appendix table 13: conversion factors of tropical livestock unit (TLU)

Livestock Category	TLU	Livestock Category	TLU
Camel	1.25	Donkey (young)	0.35
Ox	1.00	Horse	1.10
Cow	1.00	Sheep (adult)	0.13
Bull	0.34	Sheep (young)	0.06
Heifer	0.75	Goat (adult)	0.13
Calf	0.25	Goat (young)	0.06
Donkey (adult)	0.7	Hen	0.013

Source: Storck, *et al.*, 1991

Appendix table 14: Checking linearity of the model

Appendix table 15: Checking het-eroscedasticity and Homoscedasticity

Appendix table 16: Checking multi-collinearity using variance inflation factor for the continuous variables

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
AGHH	1.42	0.703018
FAMSIZ	1.39	0.719444
TNBROWN	1.32	0.755864
NULPS	1.25	0.800052
DSTNRMKT	1.16	0.860838
DSTMRT	1.11	0.903732
LNDHLD	1.09	0.913672

Source: Own computational result, 2015

Appendix table 17: checking multi-collinearity using contingency coefficient for categorical variable

Variable	SHHH	EDUCHHD	BT	FS	CRDTACS	EXTSRV	MRKTINF
SEHH	1.0000						
EDUCHHD	-0.0353	1.0000					
BT	0.0265	-0.0281	1.0000				
FS	-0.0947	0.0361	0.0533	1.0000			
CRDTACS	-0.0548	-0.0882	0.0309	0.1195	1.0000		
EXTSRV	0.0218	-0.2089	0.1105	0.0987	0.1100	1.0000	
MRKTINF	0.2599	0.1122	0.0781	0.0818	0.0241	0.1307	1.0000

Source: Own computational result, 2015

Appendix table 18: mean difference between continuous variable using t=test value

variable	Test Value = 0				
	T	Df	Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
				Lower	Upper
AGHHD	52.451	99	40.730	39.19	42.27
FAMSIZ	27.396	97	6.347	5.89	6.81
LNDHLD	20.491	99	2.380	2.15	2.61
NULPS	23.406	99	6.330	5.79	6.87
TNBROWN	27.067	99	2.870	2.66	3.08
DSTNBEFCMK	3.599	99	15.0	4.85	16.75
DSTMBEFCMK	17.538	99	22.0	117.51	147.49
DSTMRCMKT	11.280	99	10.0	32.35	46.15

Source: own survey, 2015

Appendix table 19: chi-square test for categorical variables

no	variables	χ^2
1	SEHH	8.561
2	BT	103.571
3	EDUCHHD	24.725
4	FS	5.432
5	CRDTACS	18.614
6	EXTSRV	20.159
7	MRKTINF	12.265

Source: Computed from own survey, 2015

Appendix table 20: sample size for determining population size

Population size	Sample size					
	Continuous data(margin of error=.03)			Categorical data (margin of error =.05)		
	Alpha=.10 t =1.65	Alpha=.05 t =1.96	Alpha=.01 t =2.58	P=.50 t =1.65	P=.50 t =1.96	P=.50 t =2.58
100	46	55	68	74	80	87
200	59	75	102	116	132	154
300	65	85	123	143	169	207
400	69	92	137	162	196	250
500	72	96	147	176	218	286
600	73	100	155	187	235	316
700	75	102	161	196	249	341
800	76	104	166	203	260	363
900	76	105	170	209	270	382
1000	77	106	173	213	278	399
1500	79	110	183	230	306	461
2000	83	112	189	239	323	499
4000	83	119	198	254	351	570
6000	83	119	209	259	362	598
8000	83	119	209	262	367	613
10,000	83	119	209	264	370	623

Source: (James *et al.*, 2001)

Appendix table 21: Sample photo during group discussion

